

SUSTAINABLE FINANCING FOR HIV AND AIDS IN SWAZILAND

Tomas Lievens

Tata Chanturidze

Faith Mamba

Alan R. Roe

With significant contributions from Gorik Ooms, Institute of Tropical Medicine in
Antwerp and Anton Kerr, the International HIV/AIDS Alliance

Oxford
Policy
Management

July 2009

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19490273>

Acknowledgements

Cooperation with NERCHA and UNAIDS Swaziland and financial support from UNAIDS are greatly acknowledged. We also thank Robert Greener, Sophia Mukasa Monico and Faith Mamba for their continuous support to this work.

The study has greatly benefited from the expertise, comments and suggestions from Nomathemba Iophe, Principal Secretary, Cabinet, Dumisani Masilela, Principal Secretary, Ministry of Finance, Khangeziwe Mabuza, Thabsile Dlamini, Mzungu, Budget Section, Ministry of Finance, Mbuso Dlamini, Principal Secretary, Ministry of Economic Planning and Development, Dumsani Shongwe, Economist, Ministry of Economic Planning and Development, the Macroeconomic Unit at the Ministry of Economic Planning and Development, Cyril Kunene, Principal Secretary Ministry of Public Service and Information, Mpendulo Mazibuko, Acting Under Secretary, Ministry of Public Service and Information, Sibusiso Sibandze, Health Planning Unit, Ministry of Health, Principal Secretary and Management Team, Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, Derek Von Wissel and the entire team at NERCHA, Peter Simelane at Swazi Med, Khosi Mthethwa, WHO, Bheki Bhembe and his team at the Central Bank of Swaziland, and numerous other individuals that have generously given their time and ideas to the study team.

Executive Summary

1. Up until recently **scarcity of resources was not an issue of prime importance in the global AIDS policy fora.**
2. However, **ODA has increased by less than anticipated** since the UN Conference on Financing for Development in Monterrey in 2002 and with the current **financial crisis** many low and middle income countries wonder if, and how, donor countries will maintain the aid levels they committed to.
3. Meanwhile, the success of ART programmes has contributed to the understanding that, on ethical grounds, AIDS programmes and particularly **ART treatment create a life-long entitlement** of HIV positive citizens on their governments. **The question how this life-time entitlement will be financed** has become particularly acute.
4. This work has examined Swaziland's current AIDS financing strategy from different angles and **four major challenges stand out in the immediate future:**
 - a. **The AIDS financing gap**, which is the need for resources minus the estimated available resources, **is important and grows over time.** In FY 2013/14 it is estimated to stand at USD 242,000,000
 - b. **The capacity of the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare to deliver quality health services to the entire population is weak.** This begs the question how additional resources for HIV and AIDS services will be spent effectively to increase health service availability to PLWHA.
 - c. Despite NERCHA's managerial capacity, **important progress can be made to better coordinate the AIDS Response.** This will make the allocation of resources more relevant, efficient and effective.
 - d. There's indirect evidence that the current financing strategy is **inequitable:** poorer PLWHA and affected households share a comparatively larger financial burden.
5. These challenges are both important and urgent. We identified **four ways in which these challenges can be addressed in the near future:**
6. **Mobilise additional resources for HIV and AIDS**
 - a. Our HIV and AIDS macroeconomic analysis suggests that the authorities can consider **allocating a larger share of public resources to the AIDS Response,** despite the deteriorating economic and fiscal climate.
 - b. The AIDS Response in Swaziland must provide additional evidence to the Ministry of Finance that the **proposed spending is carefully prioritised and evidence-driven; feasible, with clear and costed implementation arrangements and be linked to functioning and sustainable systems for monitoring, evaluation and management for results.**
 - c. **A multisectoral approach** is typically a route into involving more actors in the fight against HIV, and therefore also additional resource mobilisation. This avenue **needs further exploring in Swaziland.**

- d. The private sector in Swaziland, from households over communities to businesses, is believed to contribute importantly to HIV and AIDS. Yet at this moment this contribution is not recorded and hardly recognised. **Efforts to understand the scope and composition of this funding source should be undertaken so that policies with incentives to stimulate private sector contributions can be developed.**
- e. **Innovative sources of funds should be examined more closely.** Especially a **Social Health Insurance Fund** and **remittance flows** have an important potential to contribute significant additional resources for the AIDS Response.
- f. An **active advocacy policy should make donors aware of Swaziland's need for additional resources** to adequately fight HIV and AIDS. The IMF and the World Bank acknowledge the perverse effects of the country's income status on its capacity to mobilise aid. The more Swaziland's can demonstrate it has done everything in its own power to maximise resource availability for HIV and AIDS, the higher the chances of success of such strategy.

7. Health system strengthening

- a. **It is now widely recognised that sustainability and the scaling up of AIDS Responses will necessitate the strengthening of health systems in most countries.** The Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Swaziland battles with myriad inter-linked problems that are unlikely to go away soon. Despite current efforts to expand health service delivery, it may be too little too late for the AIDS Response.
- b. **The central question is whether enough is currently being done to increase the capacity of the HIV and AIDS service delivery system in Swaziland so that an additional dollar for HIV and AIDS is effectively and efficiently spent.** Given the tremendous problems of its health system, the answer is likely negative. Therefore it should be seriously considered to allocate more resources mobilised within the AIDS Response to health system strengthening.

8. Increase Civil Society Organisations' involvement in policy and delivery

- a. **CSO are generally too weakly involved in the HIV and AIDS policy planning processes of the AIDS Response in Swaziland.** However, the only way to ensure long term sustainability of the national HIV and AIDS policy is to associate all national stakeholders in the process.
- b. Because of the weak implementing capacity in the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare and the CSO, NERCHA has stepped in as an implementing partner, but this cannot be a sustainable long term approach, as it prevents NERCHA from ensuring effectively its coordination function. **Therefore it is imperative that CSO are strengthened, so that they, alongside the private for profit sector and the Ministry of Health, can ensure the delivery of sufficient quality HIV and AIDS services to PLWHA and affected households.**

9. Introduce a Programme Based Approach

- a. While improvements have been made in aligning AIDS policies and M&E systems of major players in the country, **the institutional arrangements of the AIDS**

Response in the resource allocation and implementation phases of the policy cycle are such that the AIDS response is only weakly effective and efficient.

- b. **Swaziland suffers from the negative consequences of a fragmented approach** including diminished country ownership, undermined national planning and budgeting processes, high transaction costs, and a missed opportunity to strengthen public planning and implementation mechanisms. At the most fundamental level these stand in the way of translating money into results.
- c. **The answer in other countries has been to move to some sort of programme based approach (PBA). Programme based approaches can take many forms going from general and sector budget support to SWAPs.** SWAPs are coordinating mechanisms where support to a particular sector is improved through better policy dialogue and coordination of aid directed to national sector plans and is often a prelude to, or comprises some form of, pooled funding and the use of public systems to disburse these funds to service providers.
- d. **Programme based approaches, however, have also met with criticism** the most important of which is that they can give rise to fiscal constraint and virtual spending caps. The recommendation of this work is therefore that a PBA approach must be well prepared, and part of that preparation is to assess the likely consequences on the fiscal sustainability position of the country. Views from national and international stakeholders on the latter are partly subjective and other countries that have gone through implementing programme based approaches in AIDS have found satisfactory solutions.
- e. Another potential downside of PBA is that the role of national agencies, in this case NERCHA, in orienting policy and allocating resources is likely to increase. **It is therefore important that civil society organisations are sufficiently associated in the policy process because they often defend the rights of marginalised groups such as MSM, commercial sex workers and IDUs that may otherwise be under-represented in the Response.**
- f. Our analysis suggests that many of **the preconditions for a SWAp are met in Swaziland**, such as an improving monitoring and evaluation system, a suitable annual national plan and a donor group that meets regularly.
- g. **The most important missing element for setting up a SWAp is political buy inn, both from national actors and donors. However, since some a SWAp will simultaneously address different severe problems in the AIDS Response, it is a particularly powerful instrument in making progress in the effective and efficient implementation of the AIDS Response in Swaziland.**

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	2
Executive Summary	3
Table of Contents	6
1 Rationale	8
2 The Epidemic and the Response in a nutshell	9
3 Funding for HIV and AIDS in Swaziland	10
3.1 National AIDS Spending Assessment	10
3.2 Public resources	14
3.3 International sources	16
The Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis	17
UN Agencies	20
The United States Government	21
European Union	23
International NGOs and Foundations	24
The Middle Income Fallacy	24
3.4 Private sources	25
Household contributions	25
Community based initiatives	26
Contributions from for-profit organisations	26
3.5 Innovative sources	28
Pooling resources for HIV and AIDS	28
Remittances	29
Other innovative sources of finance	30
4 HIV and AIDS financing gap	31
5 Space for future funding for HIV and AIDS	33
6 The HIV and AIDS policy cycle	35
6.1 Context	36
6.2 Content	37
6.3 Policy cycle analysis	38
6.3.1 Issue identification, analysis, consultation and planning	38
6.3.2 Coordination and oversight	39
6.3.3 Resource allocation and financial flows	40
6.3.4 Implementation	43
6.3.5 Monitoring and Evaluation	44
7 Absorptive capacity	46
8 Equity	49
9 Building blocks of an HIV and AIDS financing strategy	50
9.1 Mobilise additional resources for HIV and AIDS	50

9.2	Health system strengthening	51
9.3	Increase Civil Society Organisations' involvement	52
9.4	Programme Based Approach	52
10	References	56

1 Rationale

Up until recently, scarcity of resources was not an issue of prime importance in the global AIDS policy fora. Indeed, exceptionalism was successfully defended on multiple grounds (Peter Piot 2008). In a breach of conventional thinking about sustainable financing for development it filtered through to the modalities of important financing mechanisms such as the Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis where the 2007 call for proposals notes: "Applicants are not required to demonstrate financial self-sufficiency for the targeted interventions by the end of the proposal term." (Gorik Ooms, Wim Van Damme et al. 2008).

During the late 1990s and early 2000s a global political momentum to 'end poverty' gave rise to two ambitious ventures of international development assistance. At the one hand there is the Millennium Development Project, with one goal specifically devoted to HIV and AIDS, at the other hand the Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis which was set up with the single purpose to make progress on three of the most important public health crises worldwide.

However, the materialisation of the political commitments has been somehow disappointing and ODA has increased by less than anticipated since the UN Conference on Financing for Development in Monterrey, in 2002. (Global development finance 2008). With the financial crisis leading to a decrease in global economic output in 2009, and ensuing massive wealth destruction, many low and middle income countries wonder if, and how, donor countries will maintain the aid levels they committed to.

Meanwhile, the success of ART programmes has contributed to the understanding that, on ethical grounds, AIDS programmes and particularly ART treatment create a life-long entitlement of HIV positive citizens on their governments. With almost all national policies to fight HIV and AIDS worldwide working towards Universal Access targets this implies that governments face important financial responsibilities, especially in countries with high HIV prevalence.

In light of the global financial crisis, which now questions the scope of future donor flows but also evidently curtails domestic financial capacity, the question how this life-time entitlement will be financed has become particularly acute.

The objective of this work is therefore to look into the question of the sustainability of finance for HIV and AIDS in Swaziland. More precisely it sets out the estimated cost of the AIDS Response against the projected available resources and suggests ways to bridge the gap. But the work goes beyond the mere 'quantity of finance'. Indeed, this work also attempts to identify ways in which more can be done with one Lilangeni for HIV and AIDS so as to maximise the impact of the scarce resources. Alongside these questions of effectiveness and efficiency, the extent to which the current AIDS financing strategy is equitable is briefly looked at.

Policy making and implementation is probably more agreeable in times of financial resource affluence. However, previous experience with crises has shown that policy space for change and innovative ideas is often greater when the going gets touch (Andrew Mold, Sebastian Paulo et al. 2009). Therefore a saying favourite with policy makers today may well be applicable to the question of sustainable finance for AIDS in Swaziland: *never waste a good crisis*.

2 The Epidemic and the Response in a nutshell

Similar to many African countries Swaziland diagnosed its first HIV case in the mid-eighties. However, unlike other countries the epidemic developed rapidly into the most important in the world with a prevalence rate of 26% in the population aged 15-49 in 2007 (Central Statistical Office and Macro International Inc. 2008). Quite recently ANC sentinel data revealed that the epidemic may be stabilising at this very high level (NERCHA 2009). Since presently HIV incidence is standing at 3% per annum, also the highest in the world, the epidemic is however not being kept at bay.

Swaziland recognised quickly the seriousness of the situation and put in place policies and institutions to confront the epidemic. Political commitment has typically been high with King Mswati III declaring HIV/AIDS a national disaster in 1999 and as reported by the UNGASS indicator capturing the extent of political support increasing between 2005 and 2007 (NERCHA 2008). Five consecutive policies were developed with the latest two multi-sectoral in nature signalling the willingness to engage all actors in addressing the epidemic. The latest development in a fast-paced period of institutional transition came with the establishment of the National Emergency Response Council for HIV and AIDS, NERCHA, in 2006.

While much has been accomplished in little time, the AIDS response is currently grappling with broad engagement and effective coordination. Active engagement and participation of relevant civil society actors has been and still is a challenge with a low and stable UNGASS score on 'efforts to increase civil society participation'. Purposeful coordination of the multitude of institutions active in the sector is inherently challenging especially in a context characterised by overall low institutional competence (World Bank 2006; The International HIV/AIDS Alliance 2007; UNAIDS and Accenture 2007; NERCHA 2008).

Swaziland is somewhat misleadingly categorised as a low middle income country. With a Gini coefficient of 50.4 it has a high income inequality. The poorest 20% of the population has a share of 4% of total income, and the richest 20% has a share of 56% (World Bank 2008). Not surprisingly a about 60% of the population lives below the poverty line and 25% of the population is in need of food aid on a regular basis. Together with pervasive poverty the high HIV prevalence leads to social indicators below what one would expect from a country with a similar income status. Moreover, their trends are mostly negative.

Life expectancy has tumbled from 60 years in 1997 to 31 years in 2004 and is projected to stand at about 30 years in 2010, the lowest in the world. A similar dramatic worsening is being observed in infant and maternal mortality indicators. IMR was at 108 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2004; MMR stood at 370 deaths per 100,000 live births. High HIV prevalence rates with only 26.5% of those needing ART actually being on ART results in an alteration of the population structure. The Human Development Index has decreased year after year since 2001. These low indicators and their worsening trends have motivated some authors to cast the situation as an emergency, requiring a proportionate policy response (World Bank 2006; Whiteside and Whalley 2007).

The current multi-sectoral plan therefore proposes to step up the effort. While the emphasis has shifted in many regards between this and the former national framework one defining characteristic stand out: the current strategy favours a results based management strategy where the various interventions are brought in line with the national response priorities and where resources are used rationally (NERCHA 2009).

3 Funding for HIV and AIDS in Swaziland

3.1 National AIDS Spending Assessment

Swaziland has carried out its first NASA for the fiscal years 2005/06 and 2006/07. This AIDS expenditure exercise tracks the moneys for AIDS from the source to the beneficiary. It is a powerful tool to understand how much was really spent, by whom, and on what and is as such clearly indispensable in coordinating a purposeful AIDS Response. The fact that the first NASA took place only recently is an indication of the still nascent but maturing nature of the AIDS policy response in Swaziland. It also omits funding from private sources, including the very important contributions from households. These may be covered in later rounds¹.

The resources available for the AIDS response increased by almost 35% between 2005/06 and 2006/07. The graph below reveals further that funds from international sources are more than 50% of the total, suggesting the Swaziland AIDS response is aid-dependent. Unless the share of domestic funding is stepped up significantly in the future, the AIDS response is vulnerable to changes in volume and conditions attached in international funding.

Figure 3.1 Sources of Funds for the Swaziland AIDS response, FY 2005/06 and FY 2006/07

The graph below zooms in on the composition of international funding. It shows that three kinds of sources stand out in their relative contribution: the Global Fund for HIV/AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis; 22 named donors and a set of donors whose contribution is individually too small to be named but yet together contribute 16% of the resources in FY

¹ The results from the NASA are made publicly available in a document with corresponding name published by NERCHA. In this document we focus on some findings that will be useful to support the further analysis.

2006/07. This picture throws up two observations that are important to the AIDS Response: (i) Since the GFAMT is the single most influential donor in Swaziland it follows that if the Global Fund moneys are directed in accordance to the National Policy then resource allocation in line with the National Response is achieved to an important extent; and vice versa and (ii) NERCHA as the Response's coordinating body is likely to achieve more policy coordination by focussing its energy on the biggest donors compared to dispersing its focus on the myriad of donors in the country (more on this later).

Figure 3.2 Composition of International Funding Sources for the Swaziland AIDS Response

The NASA also examines the flow of resources from Funding Sources to Financing Agents. Financing Agents collect financial resources from Funding Sources and then select providers to which they channel these resources. These providers are located in certain areas, offer a package of services, to a typical client population. Financing Agents will additionally attach some conditions regarding effectiveness and efficiency to the resources made available to the providers. Given its importance in resource allocation the Financing Agent – Provider relationship is central in the AIDS Response, and impacts heavily on its overall effectiveness, efficiency and extent of equity. Figure 3.3 below shows that in Swaziland more than half of the Financing Agents are international in nature. In fact the Financing Agent function is taken on by a number of donors (Funding Sources) who pass on the available resources directly to service providers. Figure 3.4 shows in turn that these providers are quasi uniquely of national origin.

This analysis suggests that international donors bypass national resource pooling mechanisms (Financing Agents). This may be for a variety of reasons including supposed effectiveness (donors think they can direct resources more precisely), efficiency (donors think they can direct resources more cheaply or rapidly) or because of perceived levels of fiduciary risk (donors lack guarantees that the resources will be used for the intended purposes). However this practice comes at a cost of diminished control of national actors such as NERCHA on the use of resources for the AIDS response.

Figure 3.3 Origin of Financing Agents in the Swaziland AIDS response

Figure 3.4 Origin of Providers in the Swaziland AIDS response

Another question is to understand if resources for AIDS are actually spent according to the strategic and programmatic areas outlined in the National Strategic Framework. To do so we

can compare relative expenditure per spending category between two years². Figure 3.5 shows that the relative importance of different spending categories has changed dramatically between the two years. For example, whereas more than 30% of resources was spent on care and support in 2005/06, this was only 20% in FY 2006/07. These variations either reflect dramatic policy changes, or may illustrate the inability to direct resources according to the strategic plan, i.e. a coordination failure. We come back on this below.

Figure 3.5 AIDS expenditure per spending category for FY 2005/06 and FY 2006/07

One of the important objectives of the NASA is to be able to track HIV and AIDS resources in different spending categories, as highlighted above. The spending categories of NASA are Prevention; Treatment; OVC; Programme management and administration strengthening; Human resources recruitment and retention; Social protection and social services; Enabling environment and community development; and HIV/AIDS related research (NERCHA 2008).

However the NASA categorisation of spending does not coincide with the categories used for AIDS allocations in the National Strategic Framework (NERCHA 2005), nor with those of the Global Fund programmes (NERCHA 2009). Moreover, the UN agencies also use their own categorization of HIV and AIDS resource allocation (United Nations 2006). This observation suggests that resource allocation in line with the National Strategic Framework could be greatly improved if the main partners would use spending categories similar to the National Plan.

Another direct implication of this observation is that the value of NASA to NERCHA is greatly reduced as it does not show how much funds were spend in the different allocation categories of the National Framework. This should be adjusted in future rounds of NASA.

² This approach hinges on the obviously limiting assumption that relative spending is not a function of total available resources.

3.2 Public resources

Public resources for HIV and AIDS are not regrouped in a separate budget vote. Since they are, on the contrary, part of different public agency's budgets, there is no clear visibility given to public HIV and AIDS spending. The immediate consequence is that even the Ministry of Finance doesn't know how much is spent by whom on HIV and AIDS in any given moment of time.

The Government has recently made progress on a policy of internal mainstreaming where it is recommended that public bodies devote 2% of their budget to workplace policies for their staff. The Public Sector HIV and AIDS Coordination Committee (PSHACC) which regroups the under-secretaries of the public bodies concerned oversees the policy. Only recently a Secretariat and a Public Sector HIV and AIDS Workplace Policy have been instated which is believed to give this initiative impetus. However, at present very few public bodies reportedly devote up to 2% of resources to workplace policy.

While the PSHACC is a positive initiative it falls short of a full mainstreaming policy, where public sector bodies would undertake outward looking activities and devote an allocate part of their expenditure budgets to implement HIV and AIDS activities in their mandated technical area. To take a typical example of teachers: a workplace policy would make sure that teachers have access to preventative and curative HIV and AIDS services. An external mainstreaming policy would endeavour teachers to seize all opportunities of prevention of HIV in their work with pupils. The former is addressed by PSHACC, the latter is not a policy of the Swaziland government.

With total public expenditure standing at E 9,546,870,000 in 2008/09, 2% would amount to E 190,937,400, which is just less than 30% of the total resources for AIDS in 2008/09. This is a surprisingly large budget and it is unclear whether the budgetary implications of this are fully thought through. Since there're at present no budget lines 'HIV and AIDS workplace policy' in the individual line ministry's budgets, rules regarding the reporting of spending should be clarified by PSHACC in collaboration with NAC.

The only source about public HIV and AIDS spending is therefore NASA, which happens to be particularly sparse with information on this topic. The Ministry of Finance, which is the ultimate source for public resources is said to have contributed as follows:

Table 3.1 Public funding for HIV and AIDS

SZL	FY 2005/06	FY 2006/07
Ministry of Finance	73,190,803	136,915,968

The NASA doesn't indicate to which financing agents these funds are distributed and whether these are purely domestic funds or comprise donor on-budget contributions. More than half of these funds are destined to OVC, suggesting that the large Ministry of Education OVC programme is by far the main beneficiary of public resources. It is recommended that future rounds of NASA explore public funding in more detail.

A last important indicator of HIV public spending in a country with an AIDS epidemic of this scale is the Health budget. The table below summarises some trends (WHO, 2009).

Table 3.2 Selected indicators of Government spending on health

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
General government expenditure on health as percentage of total government expenditure (%)	11.6	11.8	8.8	13.2	12.6	10.9	9.4
Per capita government expenditure on health (PPP int. \$)	171	178	143	212	248	231	219
General government expenditure on health as percentage of total expenditure on health (%)	58.6	61	53.8	61.3	67.2	64.1	62

General government expenditure on health as a percentage of total government expenditure should be benchmarked against the Abuja target subscribed to by the Government of 15%. In 2000 this stood at almost 12%; but then evolved erratically to decline since 2003 to almost 9% in 2006. Per capital public spending on health has declined since 2004 as has the government expenditure as a percentage of total expenditure. The last indicator suggests that the private sector, mainly households, is increasingly financing the burden of health care since 2004.

The picture that emerges is that the Government of Swaziland budget for health has decreased since 2003/2004. Where levels of spending are not dramatically low compared to other African countries, they fall short of the population health care needs, such as expressed in international commitments like the Declaration of Abuja. The Government is nonetheless determined to raise levels of health spending by 2% per year from FY 2009/2010 to meet the Abuja target. The decrease in health spending witnessed over the last year is therefore not an expression of faltering political will but rather due to the incapacity of the Ministry of Health to spend additional resources (more on this later). The Ministry of Finance identified the lack of absorption capacity as one of the key challenges for allocation additional resources to the Ministry of Health (Ministry of Finance 2008).

HIV and AIDS is a cross cutting theme in the Ministry of Health budget. There's no single line item or sub-head devoted to HIV and AIDS. The drawback of this otherwise sound approach is that HIV and AIDS has no visibility in the budget and that monitoring of expenditure is very difficult to put in practice.

With these base data it is difficult to develop a perspective on future public contributions to HIV and AIDS. It is important to note that the political will to spend on HIV and AIDS, and on health in general has been outlined in different policy documents. A prudent approach would therefore be to apply the growth rate of national overall public expenditure in the MTEF planning period to the in NASA as public identified resources. This provides the following picture³.

³ The growth rate of Total public expenditure such as reported in the Budget Outlook Paper is applied to public funding for HIV and AIDS in FY 2006/07 such as reported in NASA.

Table 3.3 Projection of public resources for HIV and AIDS, FY 2006/07 to FY 2011/2012

SZL	FY 2006/07	FY 2007/08	FY 2008/09	FY 2009/2010	FY 2010/2011	FY 2011/12
Ministry of Finance	136,915,968	161,964,618	204,137,978	227,391,143	244,157,692	262,075,336

3.3 International sources

This section looks into the contributions of international sources to HIV and AIDS spending in Swaziland. Given the myriad of donors we focus on those institutions that together contribute 80% of the funds in FY 06/07.

The table below gives an overview of international contributions for HIV and AIDS by the major international donors in 2008, broken down where possible over four broad spending categories: Prevention, Treatment & care, Impact mitigation and Management & coordination.

Table 3.4 Allocation of funds for HIV/AIDS by major International contributions in 2008, Swaziland

Sources of Funds	Global Fund	UN Agencies	US Government	European Union	Int. NGOs and Foundations
	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Funding agencies	NURCHA	UNAIDS, UNDP, UNFPA, UNICEF, WHO, FAO, WFP,	USAID, CDC	IPAC, FRC, ICOSPE.	BMS, ICRC, MSF, Aaid, CF
Amount of Support	\$17,2 M*	\$ 6,5 M	\$12,7 M	Euro 2.8M	US\$1,56 M***
PREVENTION	1,961,406	1,621,360		400,000	
TREATMENT	9,248,500	1,587,680		1,500,000	
IMPACT MITIGATION	3,682,620	2,306,000		600,000	
MANAGEMENT, COORDINATION, M&E	2,355,958	1,029,400		300,000	
*Source: NERCHA Annual report 2007/2008; (E139,1 million; exchange rate 1E=0.124US\$); this allocations are done in 2007/2008					
** Source: European Union, Feb, 2009; (Euros 2,8 Million; exchange rate 1US\$=1.3Euro)					
***Source: NERCHA, Feb, 2009 (Euros 1.02 million; exchange rate 1US\$=1.3 Euro)					

The sections below provide some further information on how donors prioritise for HIV and AIDS allocations within their total aid allocations, and provide funding prospects for 2009 and beyond.

The Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis

The Global Fund supports HIV and AIDS activities in Swaziland since 2002/03. The country has participated in four Rounds of Global Fund grants and received approval of programmes for a total budget of 134,9 million US dollars.⁴ Table 3.5 presents the financial information per round for the period 2003-2008.

Table 3.5 Portfolio of GF Grants to Swaziland, HIV and AIDS, 2003-2008

Portfolio of GF Grants to Swaziland, HIV/AIDS				
Rounds	Programme	Fund Request	Approved	Disbursed
R 2	NERCHA	\$52,544,145.00	\$52,544,145.00	\$49,276,920.00
R 4	NERCHA	\$45,839,731.00	\$45,839,731.00	\$11,566,190.00
R 7	NERCHA	\$81,866,490.00	\$28,380,316.00	\$2,310,374.00
R 8	NERCHA	\$15,136,442.00	\$8,180,726.00	0
Total:		\$195,386,808.00	\$134,944,918.00	\$63,153,484.00

Tomas, I added the table on GF spending in 2007/2008 in case you need to see figures in (E) by reported NERCHA

GF spending on HIV/AIDS in Swaziland in 2007/2008 (in E)	
Expense category	Amount
PREVENTION	15,817,790
TREATMENT	74,584,678
IMPACT MITIGATION	29,698,548
MANAGEMENT, COORDINATION, M&E	18,999,649
Total:	139,100,665

The way the Global Fund determines allocations and priorities for individual countries are described in the "Comprehensive Funding Policy"⁵ paper. Technical merit is the main criterion driving proposal approval. If insufficient resources are available to fund all proposals recommended by the technical review panel (TRP), then a composite index is used to assign the scores to TRP recommended proposals. The composite index is defined as described in the Table below where disease burden and poverty level are the two key criteria to determine whether a country and the proposal are eligible for a grant when resources are insufficient.

⁴ <http://www.theglobalfund.org/>

⁵ Global Fund, Comprehensive funding policy;

http://www.theglobalfund.org/documents/comprehensive_funding_policy.pdf

Criteria	Indicator	Value	Score
Disease Burden	Eligibility criteria for proposals from Upper-Middle Income countries (applied to all proposals)	“Very high”	4
		Not “very high”	1
Poverty	World Bank Classification	Low Income Lower-Middle Income Upper-Middle Income	4 2 0

On account of Swaziland having the highest epidemic in the world, the country is a high priority for the Global Fund. Therefore Global Fund support is expected to accelerate in 2009-2010. Table 3.6 presents the GF funding projections for the coming five years, excluding the Round 8:

Table 3.6 GF funding for HIV and AIDS in Swaziland, excluding round 8, 2009-2014

Current Global Fund Funding Excluding Round 8, TB and Malaria								
Objectives	Category	SDA	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	TOTAL
Prevention	Safe sexual behaviour change	Community outreach	456,852	532,438	181,777	199,955	219,950	1,590,972
		Mass Media	261,957	278,033	314,757	346,233	380,856	1,581,836
		Condom distribution	30,000	412,971	710,246	849,982	1,010,562	3,013,761
		Male Circumcision			149,933	159,720	175,692	485,345
		STI diagnoses	42,143					42,143
	Community outreach	287,766	111,406				399,172	
	Prev: PMTCT NBTC	Prevention: PMTCT	686,598	340,574	382,082	234,394	257,834	1,901,482
	Safe blood	810,573	780,811	133,708	147,078	161,786	2,033,956	
Treatment and Care	ART	Treatment: ARV and m	2,941,402	3,654,543	939,616	1,029,064	1,758,289	10,322,914
		ARVs	6,597,909	2,331,076				8,928,985
		Drugs, PMT	334,937	183,678				518,615
		Storage capacity for ART sites	467,943	49,783				517,726
	Laboratory	HR	742,053	731,128	505,769	536,115	568,282	3,083,347
		Diagnoses	4,422,706	3,403,904	1,754,780			9,581,390
	HTC	Prevention, testing and	250,714	180,000	198,000	217,800	239,580	1,086,094
	Home based	HBC materials	1,535,503	1,053,456	599,162	659,078	724,986	4,572,185
	Palliative Care	Palliative care drugs	274,055	124,879				398,934
		Palliative care -trainers salary	52,886	20,743				73,629
Impact Mitigation	Community strengthening for OVC Support	Support child protection	776,276	434,194	1,954,990	1,779,635	1,618,968	6,564,063
		ECCD	310,158					310,158
		Compensation for Community social Centres	466,286	352,629				818,915
		Compensation for Care givers	2,821,928	2,371,991				5,193,919
	OVC Feeding	NCP Construction and	2,234,277	3,614,272	1,851,500	372,900	410,190	8,483,139
		School feeding	1,171,089	1,576,736	2,281,251	2,526,973	2,801,635	10,357,684
		NCP feeding	473,350	2,082,672	3,682,894	4,051,184	4,456,302	14,746,402
		Farm Inputs- Indlunkhulu	1,537,202	1,426,119				2,963,321
		School Gardens	541,252	19,418				560,670
	OVC Education Support	School Fees	327,408					327,408
		Compensation for teachers	147,472	99,877				247,349
		Counselling of abused children in schools	284,271	261,280	271,178	298,296	287,171	1,402,196
	PLWHA support	PLWHA	SE:: Strengthening Civil society and institutional capacity building	579,979	529,145	583,647	642,012	706,213
Mainstreaming M&E	Mainstreaming M&E	SE :Policy development,	280,800	85,234	366,465	403,112	281,849	1,417,460
		M&E	1,430,675	1,427,085	518,631	36,421	328,678	3,741,490
Administration	administration	PR administration	370,373	234,989	416,492	401,494	415,324	1,838,672
TOTALS			33,948,792	28,705,064	17,796,878	14,891,446	16,804,147	112,146,327

NERCHA assumes the role of Principal Recipient for GF funding. At the same time NERCHA is involved in service delivery for certain components of the Global Fund programmes. This creates tensions within between NERCHA and some sub-recipients in the management of grants. (more on this in sections 6.3.2. and 6.3.3.).

UN Agencies

The latest United Nations Development Assistance Framework (UNDAF) covering the period 2006-2010 describes the United Nations support to the Kingdom of Swaziland. It identifies five priority areas of cooperation one of which is HIV and AIDS. However, the five priority areas are also seen as “part of a single priority to address the complex nature of the multi-faceted HIV and AIDS crisis facing the country” (MoEP&D and UN resident coordinator 2005). The HIV/AIDS programme aims to achieve “a strengthened and intensified multi-sectoral national response to HIV and AIDS. It defines four country programme outcomes, which the individual members of the UN system present in Swaziland contribute to:

- i) reduced risk behaviour in the population;
- ii) increased access to services, commodities and supplies;
- iii) strengthened safety nets for vulnerable groups;
- iv) improvements in systems and structures at all levels.

These programmatic objectives are translated in funding allocations that fall into four broad categories: Prevention; Treatment, care and support; Impact mitigation and Management, Coordination and M&E.

The UNDAF priorities are determined by the UN country team which “has been sensitive to the national context, endeavouring in its analysis of the country needs, to be informed and guided by the priorities of both National development policies, strategies and the achievement of the Millenium development goals”⁶.” (MoEP&D and UN resident coordinator 2005) UNDAF is further informed by the National Policies and the strategies designed to reaching the Millennium Development Goals. It is also inspired by the UN Reform Agenda, in terms of addressing national development goals, including “harmonization, collaboration and joint programming.”

The preparatory process for the UNDAF includes setting up an inter-agency working group, consisting of UN agency technical staff, government counterparts, development partners, NGOs and civil society groups. The Draft UNDAF is presented to the Government and a wide range of stakeholders. The UNDAF is then further refined in UNDAF preparatory workshops and a final paper is again presented to the same stakeholders. The relative importance given to HIV and AIDS, as well as the allocation of resources to the different programmatic areas within HIV and AIDS is therefore the result of a joint process involving government agencies, bilateral and multilateral donors and civil society.

The next table presents the budget for HIV and AIDS by category required as per the annual UN Work Plan for 2008 (United Nations 2008) which totals to 11,298,070 USD. This figure is very different from actually committed resources which only reach 6,545,000 USD in 2008. The difference is ultimately due to issues of absorptive capacity (more on this in section 7).

⁶ UNDAF, 2006-2010, Kingdom of Swaziland, 2006

Table 3.7 Required UN Budget for HIV/AIDS by funding categories, 2008

REQUIRED UN Budget for HIV/AIDS Funding by Categories, 2008							
Sources of Funds	UNDP	UNFPA	UNAIDS	UNICEF	FAO	WHO	WFP
TOTAL Support in 2008	\$ 169,000	\$ 813,900	\$ 419,570	\$ 2,529,600	\$ 658,600	\$ 943,000	\$5,764,400
PREVENTION		733,900	5,000	968,000		225,000	648,000
TREATMENT/ CARE/ SUPPORT	97,000					290,000	756,000
IMPACT MITIGATION		80,000	238,000	1,211,600	658,600	5,000	3,517,200
MANAGEMENT, COORDINATION, M&E	72,000		176,570	350,000		423,000	843,200

The table below provides the break-down of total UN funding for HIV and AIDS per UN agency for the period 2006 – 2010 amounting to 33,525,000 USD. Though little firm information is known about the next UNDAF period 2011-2015, meetings with the UN representatives and the recommendations of the Joint review of the NSP 2006-2008 indicate that the thematic priorities are likely to be maintained in the upcoming period. Given the UN funding process there are no data available to indicate the scope of the support from 2011 onwards. However, the UN representatives interviewed have signalled that it will be difficult to maintain the current levels of financing.

Table 3.8 Proposed UN Funding for HIV/AIDS by Categories, 2006-2010

Proposed UN Funding for HIV/AIDS by Categories, 2006-2010							
Sources of Funds	UNDP	UNFPA	UNAIDS (secretariat)	UNICEF	FAO	WHO	WFP
TOTAL Support in 2006-2010	\$ 1,150,000	\$1,640,000	\$2,100,000	\$ 9,600,000	\$3,500,000	\$ 3,500,000	\$ 12,000,000
PREVENTION		690,000	900,000	1,300,000			100,000
TREATMENT/ CARE/ SUPPORT	1,150,000	650,000	200,000	3,050,000	250,000	3,500,000	3,800,000
IMPACT MITIGATION		100,000		3,400,000	3,000,000		8,000,000
MANAGEMENT / COORDINATION ,M&E		200,000	1,000,000	1,850,000	250,000		100,000

The United States Government

Support from the US government to HIV and AIDS in Swaziland comes through the “President’s Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR). PEPFAR differentiates countries getting US government support into two categories: “Focus Countries” and “Other bilateral Countries for HIV and AIDS programmes”. The first group gets the largest support from the US government which goes beyond the area of HIV and AIDS. Swaziland is categorized as an “Other PEPFAR member country”. Still, support given to Swaziland from PEPFAR is distinctively high in comparison with other PEPFAR countries, such as shown in Table 3.9.

with total approved allocations for Other Member countries for Fiscal Years 2006 to 2008 (PEPFAR 2008).

The allocation of PEPFAR funds over programmatic areas is mainly directed by PEPFARs directive to spend in areas where evidence about effectiveness is available but country priorities and programme costs are also taken into account to allocate resources. Overall, 22% of the total PEPFAR budget is allocated to prevention, 30% care, and 48% to treatment (PEPFAR 2008).

Table 3.9 FY 2006-2007 Funding for Other PEPFAR Countries

Table 7: FY 2006-2008 Funding for Other PEPFAR Countries

Table 7 shows the total approved allocations for these countries or regions from all sources, FY 2006 through FY 2008.

	FY 2006	FY 2007	FY 2008
	Total Funding All Sources	Total Funding All Sources	Total Funding All Sources
AFRICA			
Algeria	-	-	75,000
Angola	5,516,000	6,140,000	6,964,360
Benin	2,277,000	2,340,000	2,288,800
Burkina Faso	-	-	100,000
Burundi	2,117,000	2,680,000	4,031,650
Cameroon	-	660,000	2,017,677
Comoros, Union of	-	-	75,000
Congo Brazzaville	175,000	-	-
Djibouti	325,000	300,000	150,000
Democratic Republic of the Congo	9,260,000	10,775,000	15,413,330
Gabon	191,700	-	150,000
Gambia, the	150,000	-	53,681
Ghana	7,291,000	6,630,000	7,455,450
Guinea	2,375,000	2,658,000	2,033,800
Lesotho	7,001,000	9,550,000	13,127,910
Liberia	1,689,000	2,360,000	3,478,130
Madagascar	2,352,000	2,030,000	2,010,850
Malawi	16,369,500	18,887,000	23,862,300
Mali	4,130,000	4,290,000	4,821,700
Mauritania	-	-	105,800
Niger	-	-	50,000
Sao Tome	50,000	-	-
Senegal	6,314,668	5,816,000	4,560,700
Sierra Leone	300,000	480,000	650,000
Sudan	5,628,000	6,885,000	9,541,869
Swaziland	7,051,000	9,000,000	12,731,960
Zimbabwe	21,957,000	23,471,000	26,366,350
Central African Regional Surveillance	387,000	-	828,109
East Africa Regional	5,141,000	2,800,000	2,777,320
Southern Africa Regional	3,251,000	3,261,000	2,333,800
West Africa Regional	7,964,000	2,280,000	2,975,700
AFR Regional	2,311,000	2,013,000	991,900
Subtotal, Africa	121,573,868	125,306,000	152,023,146

Source: PEPFAR OPERATIONAL PLAN; June 2008

PEPFAR support to Swaziland for 2009 doubled in comparison to 2008 reaching 27.8 million USD of which 13,5 Million USD approved and 14,3 million US\$ requested⁷. The programme

⁷ PEPFAR team presentation Swaziland Country Operational Plan for FY09, 2009

addresses almost all areas of HIV and AIDS. Figure 3.6 presents the allocation of resources per spending category.

Figure 3.6 PEPFAR HIV/AIDS Funding for Swaziland by categories, FY 2009

Source: PEPFAR team presentation Swaziland Country Operational Plan for FY09, 2009

Projections for 2010-2015 are not formally released, as PEPFAR plans on an annual base. However meetings with PEPFAR officials suggest that the 2009 funding level would be maintained in the following five years because the epidemic is not brought under control and PEPFAR believes that the country will need continued important international support to do so. However, taking into account the impact of the global economic crisis PEPFAR contributions are not expected to increase over this period.

European Union

The primary objective of the EU development policy in Swaziland is the “eradication of poverty in the context of sustainable development, in line with the international agenda, and with particular attention to the Millennium Development Goals” (MOEP&D and the European Community 2007). The Strategy rests on three pillars, including “improved access to basic social services (health, education), in the frame of Focal Area I: Human development”.

The programme is supported by the 10th European Development Fund (EDF) and as far as its health component is concerned covers support to the reinforcement of primary health care; improving access to health services by disadvantaged groups; improvements in the National programme for the implementation of the Declaration of Commitment on HIV/AIDS; improving HIV/AIDS related behaviour; and reducing HIV rates and its associated morbidity. Most of the interventions are health systems strengthening and capacity building related.

The total budget allocated by the EDF over the period 2008-2013 is 17.5 Million Euro but in 2008 no allocations from this programme have yet been made. Nevertheless, the EU contributed 2.8 million Euro in 2008 in the area of HIV and AIDS through the “Non-State actors support programme”. As with many other development partners the EU does not account for HIV and AIDS funds separately but rather classifies expenditures according to other dimensions challenging the tracking and prediction of funds for AIDS.

International NGOs and Foundations

Following the NASA the contributions from international NGOs and foundations in FY 2005/06 and FY 2007/08 were respectively USD 3,2 million and USD 7,0 million (NERCHA 2008). However the figure is probably higher in reality as it doesn't comprise for example the support from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, USD 10 Million for male circumcision over 5 years. Nor are contributions from the Clinton Foundation, the “Clinton HIV/AIDS Initiative” since 2005⁸ or the programmes from Medecins Sans Frontieres included in this figure. Future NASA rounds are likely to increase their accuracy.

The Middle Income Fallacy

Per capita income is an important proxy for a country's wealth and used to determine a country's income status. Because of its GDP per capita of \$5,635 Swaziland is classified as a middle income country ranked 105 out of 146 countries. This measure however does not take into account how wealth is distributed within the country. With a Gini coefficient of 50.4 Swaziland has severe income inequality and can rather be seen as a poor and rich country in one, with about 60% of the population living under the poverty line.

The combination of pervasive poverty and the highest HIV prevalence level in the world not surprisingly affects its social indicators, which are lower compared to other middle income countries and are rather closer to those of low-income countries.

Country	GDP capita 2007	Per (\$),	HIV/AIDS Prevalence (Adult population, 2007)	Crude Death Rate (per 1000), 2007	Life Expectancy at birth, 2007	Infant Mortality, 2007
Lesotho	1,542		23.2	19.2	43	84
Ethiopia	779		2.1	14	53	75
Kenya	1,713		9.8	12	54	80
Mozambique	896		11.9	19.8	42.4	96
Swaziland	5,635		25.1	21	40	66
Namibia	6,577		15.3	12	53	47
Botswana	14,882		23.9	14	51	33
South Africa	10,119		18.1	17	50	46

Source: World Development Indicators database

⁸ Clinton HIV and AIDS Initiative <www.clintonfoundation.org/download/?guid=82cd54a6-98de...>

Swaziland income status has an important impact on international donor funding. First, Swaziland is not eligible for Bretton Woods grant and soft loan financing. Second, it distorts the perception of donors and the international community at large of the real needs of the population which, clearly, are largely unmet.

The Ministry of Finance is currently in the process of negotiating the revision of this classification, and argues that special consideration needs to be made for a country with such levels of poverty. The IMF, in its Article IV consultation (IMF 2004), as well as the World Bank in its HIV/AIDS Agenda for Action (World Bank 2007) recognise that the limited access to donor funding as a result of the country's income status is at odds with the country's financial needs to fight the epidemic and that innovative action must be taken to remedy this situation.

3.4 Private sources

The National AIDS Spending Assessment did not investigate the contribution of private sources to the AIDS response. Yet, this contribution is believed to be very significant. Private sources typically include contributions from for profit and not-for profit organisations, private health care and households. This study does not fill the lack of data for Swaziland but attempts to bring together some information to indicate the scope of the contributions of this sector.

Household contributions

The WHO estimates that 14.5% of total health expenditure in Swaziland is contributed out-of-pocket (2005). While this partly comprises contributions of richer households to private for profit providers it also includes contributions from poor households to public and faith based providers. Part of these contributions are made by HIV and AIDS patients for HIV and AIDS health services, however precise figures for Swaziland are not available.

Several countries have done assessments of household contributions to health care related HIV and AIDS services, which are a sub-section of the AIDS response. Even though contributions vary from country to country, household contributions tend to be invariably high:

- In Rwanda in 1998, 93% of HIV/AIDS specific health expenditure was paid for out-of-pocket by households (UNAIDS 2001);
- Household out-of-pocket expenditure on HIV and AIDS in Malawi was 4.4% of the total resources for HIV and AIDS in FY 2004/05. Although not so high as in some other countries, household direct out-of-pocket spending by PLWHA is still the major private sector financing agent of HIV and AIDS accounting for 35% of total private sector spending. This is disturbingly high especially since the cost of ART being highly subsidized in 2002/03 and free since then at a multitude of donor-funded facilities (Ministry of Health and Abt Associates 2007)
- In 2002 households in Kenya, Rwanda and Zambia paid respectively 26%, 16% and 25% towards the total HIV and AIDS related health expenditure. Most of these (more than 90%) were out-of-pocket expenditure, amounting to respectively 55USD⁹, 46USD and 50 USD per adult PLWHA per year. In comparison with the general population, PLWHA spend 2.6; 3.6 respectively 5.9 times more out-of-pocket on

⁹ Purchasing power parity

health services than the general population (Ministry of Health and PHRplus 2005; De 2006)

These findings suggest that it is important that household contributions are included in the next NASA round if a comprehensive and realistic picture of the sources for AIDS expenditure are to be understood. These findings also suggest important equity considerations, which are looked at in more detail in section 8.

Community based initiatives

Communities typically play an important role in supporting affected and infected households through myriad initiatives. This has been widely documented for Africa (ONUSIDA 1999). Swaziland is certainly rich in community based initiatives such as Neighborhood Care Points, Indlunkhulu Fields, KaGogo social centres, and numerous other forms of community services for people living with HIV, psychosocial support programmes and outreach services. These have been the object of a UNAIDS Best Practice publication 'Helping ourselves: Community responses to AIDS in Swaziland' (UNAIDS 2006).

The financial value of these community services is not easily determined. But given the sheer volume of community 'service providers' and beneficiaries involved it is very significant and the funds required to finance the AIDS Response would be significantly higher if these services were to be provided by professional service providers.

Public policy is important to support these initiatives. They can benefit from financial incentives and support, capacity building and professionalization, linking them to networks of professional service providers and so on. While these services are valuable for other reasons than purely financial ones, their financial worth is a sufficient reason to adequately support those community based services that are an integral part of the National Strategic Framework.

Contributions from for-profit organisations

The participation in and contribution from private companies to the AIDS Response is such that SWABCHA – the Swaziland Business Coalition on HIV/AIDS has been created in 2001 in an effort to respond to the rising burden and impact of HIV/AIDS in the work environment and surrounding communities.

SWABCHA works as a secretariat to companies that have dedicated resources for HIV and AIDS. Its current membership is 80 companies, of which 20 large and 60 SMEs. SWABCHA's main activities are: (i) coordinating and facilitating the private sector response; (ii) advocacy, to promote and mobilize for HIV prevention in the private sector; (iii) supporting private sector involvement in the fight against HIV through the provision of advice and information; facilitation of company trainings, and facilitation of impact mitigation strategies and (iv) monitoring the private sector response. It also links with NERCHA where it represents the private sector.

Currently commercial businesses' involvement in HIV and AIDS is through three channels:

Workplace programmes - mainly targeted at HIV prevention including awareness raising workshops and meetings, distribution of condoms and IEC training of peer educators and provision of Voluntary Testing and Counselling services and development of workplace policies and programmes. A rapid assessment of the private sector response to HIV found the following that only 106 businesses out of 886 (12%) have a workplace programme. Of

the 12% that have workplace programmes, approx 50% provide some form of care and support for employees.

In-house health centers – there are different examples including:

- ✓ The Royal Swaziland Sugar Corporation (RSCC) controls over 66% of Swaziland's sugar production and has a significant role in the development of Small Scale Sugar Cane Production. In addition to workplace programmes and policies aimed at preventing HIV in the workplace, and also realizing the magnitude of HIV and AIDS programme on its employees, the sugar growing companies initiated a prevention and care programme which covers VCT, ARV's, PHC and condom distribution. This programme is extended to employees (approximately 3600), their dependents and surrounding communities. With the support of the drugs received through the Global Fund and NERCHA ARV's are made available free of charge at company clinics. Sugar growing companies that provide similar services include Tambankulu sugar estates, ILLOVO; although both refer employees requiring ART to the nearest hospital for free ARVs.
- ✓ SAPPI is an international forest products company and the world's largest producer of coated wood, paper and dissolving pulp. In Swaziland SAPPI employs approximately 1700 people. Through the company's 3 integrated clinics located on the mill the company provides a comprehensive HIV programme that is totally integrated within the health care system, provides VCT and ART, and is not only accessible to its employees but also to their dependents and surrounding communities. Because of the part support received from NERCHA/Global Fund the company is able to provide free VCT and ART.
- ✓ Conco/ Coca Cola produces concentrate and juice beverages, it has approx 152 full time employees. Conco does not have a clinic on site but has contracted Life Works, a South African based company, to monitor and administer their entire HIV programme. Life Works provides a range of comprehensive and fully managed medical and risk management services VCT and ART, patient monitoring etc are provided through this programme. This programme is limited to employees of the company.
- ✓ Swazimed, a private health insurer, presently covers about 42,000 individuals in Swaziland, mainly through contracts with companies that offer health insurance as a benefit to their workers. About one thousand of these individuals are HIV+ and therefore gain access to Swazimed's innovative scheme 'Aids for Aids' which pays for diagnostic HIV related interventions and ART, without increasing the insurance premium for the concerned member. 'Aids for Aids' yearly budget is around E5,000,000. Swazimed estimates that the market for this insurance product is not fully explored and that at least 20,000 more individuals could be reached. This excludes not only civil servants but also lower paid workers of which there're at least 20,000 (with dependents a population of approximately 70,000 individuals). While the long term sustainability of the scheme is as yet unclear, as it is presently financed out of reserves and issues such as adverse selection have not been examined in any detailed way, the scheme does illustrate that significant resources can be mobilised by private health insurers. Public policy such as linking it up to the Social Health Insurance to be set up, or by giving it financial incentives, or ensuring collaboration with local HIV and AIDS service providers, could leverage this kind of initiatives significantly and ensure additional resources for the AIDS Response.

Charity – ad hoc contributions to HIV and AIDS affected households.

When set out against the scope of the business sector in Swaziland the involvement of businesses in HIV and AIDS is only in its infant stage.

Although by no means representative of the sector's contribution to HIV and AIDS, SWABCHA provided some figures on some company's estimated HIV and AIDS programmes, for illustrative purposes:

	2007	2008
Sappi Usuthu	-	50,000
RSSC	60,000	100,000
Standard Bank	60,000	-
Nedbank	20,000	-
SWD Water Services	-	30,000
Ubombo Sugar	60,000	25,000
SPTC	10,000	15,000
Swaziland beverages	-	15,000
FSECC	100,000	100,000

3.5 Innovative sources

In this section we briefly look at potential new sources of funding for HIV and AIDS. It is difficult to assess the potential size of contribution that could be generated through these sources

Pooling resources for HIV and AIDS

Financing mechanisms that pool resources for health, such as social health insurance or insurance for targeted populations such as civil servants, not arithmetically generate additional resources for health. However, they have the important characteristic that contributions are predictable and often broken down in small payments affordable to members, be it organisations or individuals, resulting in health care being better accessible for the covered population in comparison with a system relying on out-of-pocket payments. Inasmuch as pooling mechanisms increase access to health care they tend to mobilise additional resources for health care.

Social health insurance is a potential financing tool for HIV and AIDS in two ways. Indirectly, since it increases access to outpatient and inpatient care which includes the treatment of opportunistic diseases of HIV positive and AIDS patients. And directly by covering HIV and

AIDS specific diagnostic and treatment interventions, inasmuch as the benefit package would include these.

The government is currently considering two schemes. One specifically targets civil servants, the other is a social health insurance that over time ambitions to cover the entire population. In terms of additional finance for HIV and AIDS the latter is obviously desirable since its population coverage is much larger.

The WHO has carried out a feasibility study for the social health insurance project, which is very well documented (WHO 2008) although key policy decisions are needed before detailed actuarial calculations can be presented. However, as it stands, the preferred option would be to cover the entire population within six years and the government would pay for those unable to pay. ART and pre-ART medical services, however, would be excluded from the benefit package as long as a more detailed understanding of their cost and utilisation rates are unknown, and as long as donors directly fund these programmes.

The current thinking about SHI in Swaziland would have important consequences for financing HIV and AIDS:

- If the SHI is set up following the specifications above, the direct result would be that after six years the entire cohort of HIV and AIDS patients see the financial barriers to accessing general outpatient and inpatient care significantly decreased, resulting in an increase access to this kind of care, which in financing terms means additional resources for HIV and AIDS. The precise share of HIV and AIDS in these health resources is difficult to estimate at this stage, but the sums involved are evidently significant in a country which such a high HIV burden.
- Because the government is meant to contribute on behalf of those that are unable to, the SHI is equity enhancing. It is therefore a more desirable financing mechanism than the present system partly based on out-of-pocket contributions.
- The WHO advises Swaziland not to include ART and pre-ART treatment in the SHI benefit package in the short term because donors are still financing these interventions directly. However, when the SHI would be established, and ART scaled up to satisfactory levels, it would be desirable from a sustainability perspective to include ART and related diagnostics in the SHI.

It is difficult to estimate the additional resources for HIV and AIDS a SHI would generate but it is clear that in a high prevalence country such as Swaziland this is significant.

Remittances

Income from remittances is believed to be very important in Swaziland. They are sent home by a cohort of emigrants estimated to be 95,608 strong and living in countries in the region or high middle income countries outside Africa. Notwithstanding difficulties to measure their scope, estimates are invariably high:

- Genesis Analytics estimates that in 2005 aid flows to Swaziland totalled USD 26.5 whereas remittance flow with 72.1 million USD largely surpassed them (Genesis Analytics 2006);

- In 2006 the IMF estimated that remittances accounted for 4.2% of the GDP of Swaziland - one of the ten highest in Africa (IMF 2006)

Throughout the region, households use remittances in different ways. In Zimbabwe 57% of remittances are spent on school expenditure (mostly fees) whereas in Swaziland 39% of the households spend it on medical expenses (Tim Hughes et al 2006).

Although some remittances are in the form of goods, they are mostly cash in Swaziland. Formal remittance channels include banks and the post office. In the past long term mineworkers used the TEBA bank - a service provided by the Employment Bureau of Africa.

Whilst migration in the past was dominated by mine workers, in recent years it has involved skilled professionals who often take on the South African nationality - making it even more difficult to track their contribution to remittance flows.

Some formal remittance channels used in Swaziland have high transaction costs and are believed to dampen the scope of money transfers. These include:

- Banking requirements often excluding migrants from accessing banking services;
- Clearance times for money transfers are notoriously long;
- Very stringent exchange controls exercised by banks in South Africa;
- A survey in 2003 found that 33% of urban and 54% of rural Swazi had no bank accounts so that migrant worker willing to remit money had to use other, likely informal, channels (Finmark Trust 2003).

Informal channels such as money carried by migrants themselves, remittances carried by friends and family, or sent through taxis and buses are believed to have a number of advantages. They tend to be cheap, particularly when compared with bank charges, avoid government taxes, do not require documentation and facilitate transfers from illegal immigrants. However they're also unsafe and are extremely difficult to monitor.

Despite the importance of remittances in Swaziland the government has made little effort to facilitate them, and enhance their developmental impact. Facilitating safe remittance transfers with low transactions costs is likely to sustain if not increase the flow of remittances, part of which are clearly used as HIV and AIDS expenditure.

Other innovative sources of finance

We have briefly examined but not withheld as having an important potential in Swaziland a number of innovative sources of finance for HIV and AIDS. These include earmarked taxes and levies – which are not seen as attractive by the current policy of the Ministry of Finance, Triangular and South-South cooperation and UNITAID. These mechanisms are described in more detail in a note by UNAIDS: Lamontagne, E. and Greener, R. (2008) Long term financing opportunities for HIV in Africa, UNAIDS.

4 HIV and AIDS financing gap

In this section we bring together the expected available resources with the resources needed to finance the AIDS Response. The latter have been developed by the NAC as part of the costing of the Action Plan.

Statements about resource projections are necessarily based on a number of assumptions which are described in A-1 and in Section 3. This projection is not meant to be definitive, but can be refined and give rise to some form of scenario planning. More detailed figures are in A-1.

As part of the costing of the Action Plan the NAC looked into future resources. While this exercise is completely independent from this one both estimates are comparatively close, as shown in the table below. This suggests that the reliability of the estimate of future resources is probably good.

<i>USD</i>	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14
Expected available resources – our analysis	113,096,309	112,641,105	105,866,856	102,961,424	104,874,125
Expected available resources – NAC analysis	102,601,488	98,697,008	96,600,133	95,124,312	92,841,707
Difference	10,494,821	13,944,098	9,266,723	7,837,112	12,032,418

The graph and table below summarise the findings.

<i>USD</i>	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14
Resource needs	151,946,636	214,089,424	282,898,017	311,187,819	342,306,600
Expected available resources	113,096,309	112,641,105	105,866,856	97,482,498	99,395,199
Financing gap	-38,850,327	-101,448,319	-177,031,160	-213,705,321	-242,911,402

It is clear that the HIV and AIDS resource gap in Swaziland is large, and growing, over the entire period considered. In FY 2013/14, only 30% of the resources needed to address HIV and AIDS are expected to be available. This calls for a downward revision in resources needed, a dramatic increase in funding for HIV and AIDS, or a combination of both.

5 Space for future funding for HIV and AIDS¹⁰

Abstracting for the moment from the possible impacts of the global crisis, the assessment of Swaziland's macroeconomic situation is broadly positive. It combines recent fiscal surpluses, high levels of revenue mobilisation, a strong build up of international reserves, an inflation rate that is only mildly worrisome, a real exchange rate that the IMF adjudges to be "broadly adequate", and a public debt burden that is low. This should provide the basis for a broadly up-beat assessment of the country's ability to absorb the very large financing challenges associated with the HIV/AIDs epidemic. However, there are **two** significant and related negative factors that have to qualify any such an assessment.

First, the strong revenue performance has been achieved largely on the back of the anomaly of the high fiscal revenues that Swaziland is able to draw from the present SACU system. In recent years this high level of revenues has been achieved in spite of a very poor rate of economic growth: a rate far too low to assure the achievement of the MDGs by 2015 and significantly lower than in the neighbouring countries of the region. Unfortunately there are several reasons for anticipating a *possible* decline in the generosity of the SACU revenue formula in the medium term and these are listed in Section 2 of this paper. These revenues will persist but there can be no assurance about the level at which they will do so. So the IMF in its 2008 assessment was quite right to place some emphasis on the trend of the fiscal balance *excluding* the SACU revenues. This exercise shows a very substantial and, more important, a deteriorating deficit through 2012 and beyond. Hence the IMF's November 2008 assessment was that Swaziland needs a modest fiscal adjustment (estimated to be of the order of 3.6% of GDP) in order to ensure the sustainability of its public finances.

The second caveat is that since end-2008 the prospective economic deterioration of the region because of the global financial crisis has worsened. As recently as July 2008 the IMF was forecasting growth for Sub-Saharan Africa as a whole in 2009 close to the 2007-achieved rate of 6.9%. But this rate was reduced to 6.3% in the October forecast and to only 1.7% in the April 2009 forecast¹¹. Even more significantly the October 2008 forecast for growth in South Africa of 3.3.% in 2009 was reduced in April 2009 to *minus* 0.3%! It is well beyond the scope of this present paper to provide a detailed re-assessment of the growth rate and fiscal numbers for Swaziland that will result from the regional deterioration. But we can be pretty sure that the effects will be negative and will take some of the gloss away from the otherwise positive assessment.

These two caveats need to be viewed in the light of AIDS financing gap (rising to \$240 million by 2013/14) in the funding so far identified for the country's HIV and AIDS programme. If this is done it indicates that there is at best a very limited scope for a large fiscal contribution to meet that shortfall.

However, in the practical world of *real politik* there is a significant ray of light that arises from the changing stances of the IFIs and the IMF in particular following the G20 summit in April 2009. The IMF has stated publicly that fiscal deficits for Sub-Saharan Africa as a whole are likely in the crisis circumstances to be on average 2% larger than would otherwise have been the case. The IMF and other donors have also realised the need for somewhat softer structural conditions on their lending and for a more concerted effort to protect critical social

¹⁰ This section reproduces the conclusions of a stand alone paper that has been produced by Alan R. Roe as part of this work 'HIV and AIDS macroeconomic framework'.

¹¹ The source is IMF, *World Economic Outlook*, in all cases.

programmes. Whereas the issues of fiscal sustainability that seem to be associated with the IMF's change of position cannot be fully engaged in this paper it worth noting that IF the IMF's pre-crisis calculations about the size of the primary balance needed for sustainability were broadly "correct", then there are certain implications that follow from that change of position. The most important of these is that the IMF itself and other international donors must be willing to provide additional *debt-free* funding to meet the difference between the pre and post-crisis views of what is a sustainable deficit.

Having reviewed various different ways to fill the HIV/AIDS funding gap, we have sketched the elements of a possible way forward. This has four main elements. First we suggest that the government should pursue the efficiency savings on expenditures and the parallel efficiency changes in its tax effort as proposed by the IMF in its 2008 review. But instead of using these improvements to run a smaller fiscal deficit the government would commit at least a part of the improvement to fund a small contribution to the HIV and AIDS Response. The balance of the savings we assume would need to be absorbed in any case to address the likely deterioration in the fiscal situation as caused by the global crisis (which was not factored in to the 2008 review of the IMF). Second, based on the evidence provided above we suggest that there is probably no real scope to divert expenditures from other government programmes. Third, we also suggest that there is only limited scope to increase further the aggregate public revenues collections – beyond the level proposed by the IMF. Fourth, we conclude, based on the earlier points, that the only real way to close the bulk of the HIV and AIDS funding gap via the budget would be for the government and donors to develop a substantial new grant-funding capacity with the funds earmarked to the HIV and AIDS effort. This would be consistent with the broad thrust of the G20 pronouncements. Specifically, at the global level, larger budget deficits are now being entertained and there is a willingness to provide more softer conditionality funds with an increasing focus on major priorities in the social sectors.

The paper has not focused at all on the practical steps needed to implement this possible way forward. But it has shown that the numbers should add up to fill the identified HIV and AIDS funding gap if such an approach were to be entertained by the authorities.

6 The HIV and AIDS policy cycle

Policy is the basis for resource allocation. In a context where resources are scarce, the choices about priorities to be financed are embedded in policies. These are developed within a policy space, where different actors with often conflicting viewpoints negotiate a final decision. Policies are often reflective of the dominant discourse and power relations and inversely of the extent to which alternative discourses and less powerful groups have been successful in impacting on the dominant viewpoints.

A key question is thus whether in Swaziland AIDS policy, plans and budgets duly reflects the views and preferences of the phenomenon of HIV and AIDS such as perceived by the different, especially national interest groups; and whether the implementation and feed-back processes contribute to an effective and efficient strategy to tackle HIV and AIDS in the country. This section tries to answer that question through a description and analysis of the policy cycle for HIV/AIDS in Swaziland.

Different analytical frameworks have been developed to unpack HIV/AIDS policy planning, implementation and evaluation (Paul A Sabatier 2007). A well known public policy framework by Lasswell and Brewer (Lasswell 1956) adapted by deLeon (DeLeon Peter and Kaufmanis Katie 2001) divides the public policy process into a number of discrete stages. In this framework the policy cycle is linear in nature and offers therefore a straightforward tool to map processes and actors. Being slightly adjusted by Bridgman and Davis, 2004, it is widely used to date by WHO (Enrico Pavignani 2009), IMPA (IMPA 2003) and other numerous international organizations and national governments.

Figure 1: An Australian policy cycle model (Bridgman & Davis, 2004)

Source: Bridgman and Davis, 2004

While we propose to use this framework we also recognise its limitations in offering no propositions on causality and for presuming linearity of the public policy process which doesn't exist in reality. Therefore we complement it with an approach developed by Walt and Gilson (1994) which points to the importance of interactions between actors, contextual features, processes, and policy content features (Walt G and Gilson L 1994; Paul A Sabatier 2007). This framework, policy triangle analysis, looks at the intersection of 'Discourse/narratives', 'Politics/Interest' and 'Actors/Networks'.

Diagram 3.2: Walt and Gilson Policy analysis triangle

Source: "Tackling implementation gaps through health policy analysis"; Regional Network for Equity in Health in east and southern Africa; EQUINET Policy series, N21. September, 2008;

6.1 Context

Swaziland macro economic analysis, the HIV/AIDS epidemic and the Response have been briefly discussed in previous sections. We will therefore focus on the country's legal environment, its overarching policy environment and the key actors involved in HIV and AIDS.

Swaziland adopted a number of legal international obligations in the sphere of HIV and AIDS. These include the UNGASS declaration of HIV and AIDS (2001); Millennium Development Goals (MDG 2000); The Abuja declaration and Plan of Action (2001); The Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination Against Women (CEDAW); The UN Convention of Rights of the Children; and The Universal Human Rights Declaration¹². All of these contribute to a supportive environment for HIV and AIDS activities in the country.

Swaziland has not updated its economic development policies recently. The National Development Strategy (NDS, 1997-2022) is developed a decade ago and doesn't reflect a number of important current realities and challenges. A PRSP was prepared in 2005 and followed with an Action Plan (Ministry of Economic Planning and Development and Poverty reduction task force 2005) that is still at the start of "preparatory work for implementation" (MOEP&D and the European Community 2007). Although more recent economic review and outlook 2007/08-2010/11 only timidly addresses HIV/ AIDS. HIV and AIDS policies have therefore only a weak policy referral cadre and are not strongly embedded in policies which are hierarchically more important and closer to the centre of Government.

Table 6.1 presents the actors involved in HIV and AIDS coordination at different levels and with different target groups in Swaziland (NERCHA 2009). Though each of these has defined functions and responsibilities their sheer number challenges NERCHA in effectively coordinating the Response overall.

¹² The national Multi-sectoral Strategic Framework for HIV and AIDS 2009-2014; Final Draft; NERCHA, The Kingdom of Swaziland; 2009

Table 6.1 Organizations involved in HIV/AIDS Coordination in Swaziland at different levels and with various target groups, 2009

	Abbreviation of Organization	Name (and entitlements) of Organization
1	NERCHA	National Emergency response Council on HIV and AIDS (with a primary role of a National coordination)
2	REMSHACCs	Regional Multi-Sectoral HIV and AIDS Coordination Committees
3	SNAP	Swaziland National AIDS Programme
4	CFFBO	The Church Forum for Faith Based Organisations
5	SNYC	The Swaziland National Youth Council (coordinating HIV programmes for Youth centres)
6	PSHACC	The Public Sector HIV and AIDS Coordinating Committee
7	AMICAALL	The Alliance of Mayors and Municipal Leaders in Africa on HIV/AIDS (a public private partnership focused on urban constituencies)
8	BCHA	The Business Coalition on HIV and AIDS (for employees in the organizations)
9	CANGO	The Coordinating Assembly on NGOs (for the civil society sector)
10	SWANNEPHA	Swaziland National Network of People Living with HIV and AIDS for People Living with HIV/AIDS
11	SUSAH	Swaziland Informed services Alliance on HIV
12	PPC on HIV/AIDS	Parliament portfolio committee on HIV/AIDS
13	MISA	Media Institute of South Africa
14	Academia	The sector of tertiary institutions addressing the needs of HIV/AIDS;
15	KU	Khulisa Umnftwana (coordinates HIV/AIDS activities in traditional sector)
16	THO	Traditional Healers Organization
17	FODSWA	federation of Disabled Persons in Swaziland
18	NCCU	National Children's Coordination Unit

Source: NERCHA Annual report 2007/08

6.2 Content

The Response to the HIV /AIDS epidemic dates back to 1987. The first HIV/AIDS plan was prepared by the MoHLSW in 1987 - 1988 and gave rise to setting up an AIDS Task Force. The task force was later on transformed into the Swaziland National AIDS Programme (SNAP) which is currently a key department in the planning and implementation of HIV and AIDS services in the MoLHSW.

The first National Strategic Plan 2000-2005 (NSP I) was developed by the Crisis Management and Technical Committee on HIV and AIDS in 1999 as a response to declaring the AIDS epidemic a national disaster. In 2001, NERCHA was established to coordinate the HIV/AIDS Response at the national level. Under leadership of NERCHA the National Multi-sectoral HIV and AIDS Strategic Plan 2006-2008 (NSP-II) was developed which guided the National Response to AIDS up to 2009.

Last year NERCHA took the initiative to develop the third National Multi-sectoral HIV and AIDS strategic Framework 2009-2014 (NSF). This is an overarching document, aimed to (i) guide the implementation of a multi-sectoral, relevant, comprehensive and effective HIV and AIDS Response in Swaziland; (ii) guide the mainstreaming of gender and Human Rights into the National Response; and (iii) enable the scaling up of evidence-based, decentralized HIV and AIDS response strategies (NERCHA 2009).

In parallel, the MoLHSW has prepared the National Health Policy (2007) in follow up of the first National Health Policy (1983), as well as a National Health Sector Strategic Plan 2008-2013 (Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 2009). These documents outline, amongst other, the ministry's policies and plans in the area of HIV and AIDS.

6.3 Policy cycle analysis

The policy cycle represents the key stages from policy design over implementation and feedback, and the ways these are interrelated. It examines the strengths and weaknesses at each stage that support or hinder the achievement of the objectives of the AIDS Response. It explores the relevance, effectiveness, efficiency and quality issues in all stages of the cycle. The following sections unpack the policy cycle and look into, respectively (i) issue identification, analysis and planning; (ii) resource allocation, budgeting and service purchase; (iii) implementation, and (iv) monitoring and evaluation. Leadership and coordination issues are also discussed as key factors contributing to the success of the Response.

6.3.1 Issue identification, analysis, consultation and planning

Swaziland has made important progress in strategic planning for HIV and AIDS. The process of preparing the last NSP II was highly participatory and based on the results of the joint review of NSP II. It was inspired by thorough analysis, consultations and planning. The guiding principles for the development of the current NSF include result-based management of the HIV response, gender equity, human rights, community participation, knowledge management, mainstreaming and coordination (NERCHA 2009).

However, a reported relative weakness remains the broad association of local communities and regions in the planning process, and lack of available data on HIV/AIDS needs from grassroots levels. This observation was also central in a previous study by Accenture (UNAIDS and Accenture 2007).

Another recurrent and seemingly intractable issue is the incapacity of the policy process to fully and meaningfully associate civil society organisations to the planning process. While on paper participatory approaches are being following, a level of disgruntlement and distrust remains between the key players including the CSO. This is illustrated in for example the UNGASS indicator "Overall, how would you rate the efforts to increase civil society participation in 2007 and 2005?" The score on this question is low, 4 (with 0 = poor and 10 = good) and even more worryingly there's no evolution between 2005 and 2007 (NERCHA 2008). The Public Expenditure Review suggests that this attitude is part and parcel of how Swaziland's public affairs ethos: "There is a lack of transparency and limited access of civil

society to information on public affairs. Another recent study (...) paints a similar picture. Access to information on public affairs is limited due to state-owned media and sanctioned reporting, while publication of detailed public information (...) is limited or outdated.” It is clear however that for national policies on HIV and AIDS to be reflective of the needs and capacities in the country, a close and meaningful association of CSOs is indispensable.

All in all the current NSF is a well elaborated document with significant improvements compared to NSP-II. However, the ultimate value of policies and strategies lies in the extent to which they can guide change on the ground. In this a number of questions remain outstanding:

- To which extent is the NSP harmonised with other social sector policies with chapters on HIV and AIDS such as health, education and social protection?
- What is the degree to which responsibilities and authority for coordination, financing, monitoring and evaluation of the different players in different policy documents are aligned?
- How realistic is a plan that remains largely mute on the need for capacity strengthening to enhance absorptive capacity, as well as on evidence for effectiveness and efficiency in a resource constrained context?

These questions are partly addressed below.

6.3.2 Coordination and oversight

The plans and policies of the different actors intervening in HIV in Swaziland appear reasonably well aligned. Coordination of policy seems therefore largely achieved. A different picture, however, emerges when it comes to institutional arrangements and responsibilities of the various players involved in coordination and oversight.

Diagram one presents the summary of the institutional set up of coordination of HIV and AIDS activities in Swaziland. It is clear, that NERCHA is expected to coordinate AIDS activities over different sectors and at various administrative levels. However, closer inspection of the mandates of for example the MoHSW and NERCHA reveals that they overlap when it comes to policy formulation, strategic planning, programming and monitoring and evaluation. This leads inevitably to frictions in the policy process.

During the expert interviews a few anecdotal examples of coordination failure were picked up. The Ministry of Education had been notified in December 2008 that the Global Fund would cease to finance primary school feeding programmes from April 2009 onwards, and that the programme therefore was to be financed out of the Ministry’s regular budget. It was only at the very last moment – and merely by coincidence – that it appeared that no provisions in the Ministry’s budget for FY 2009/10 had been made. This case is reportedly not a stand alone and the smooth transition of funding from international donors to regular public budget is often difficult to ensure. Ultimately, coordination failure impacts negatively on the beneficiaries.

Diagram 1: Summary of Coordination, NERCHA, 2008

Source: NERCHA Annual report 2007/08.

NERCHA is expected to have the capacity and organizational set up to carry out successfully multiple complex functions including coordination, programme management and financing, proposal development, monitoring and evaluation, and mastering moreover the administrative and financial procedures that come with being a PR for the Global Fund. While progress has been made, important capacity constraints remain to be resolved (NERCHA 2008) and the organisation is still shouldered by key-individuals rather than by systems.

Lastly, even if NERCHA is successful to some extent in coordinating the Response, its current set-up may be to revision over time as bringing the functions of coordination, financing and implementation into a single organisation likely creates conflicts of interests.

6.3.3 Resource allocation and financial flows

In order to understand the resource allocation patterns and financial flows for HIV and AIDS, this section highlights the Sources of Funding, Financial agents, Recipients of funds and the beneficiaries (population groups). It describes key spending categories for resource allocations to HIV and AIDS. Further, it analysis systemic arrangements for financial flows, and links this with accountability issues and role distribution for Coordination Function among different actors. Finally, it attempts to discuss main bottlenecks related to HIV/AIDS recourse allocation and financing.

Funding Flows

Figure 6.1 below illustrates the complexity of the current arrangements of financing for HIV and AIDS. NERCHA receives funds mainly from the government and the Global Fund a significant proportion of which are channelled to public health care providers and public schools which, however, are administratively accountable to their line Ministries (designated as 'high accountability'). Most of the funds received by the MoHSW through NERCHA go directly to SNAP, who coordinates HIV and AIDS within the ministry. Whereas SNAP takes resource allocation decisions, the transactions of funds are administered by NERCHA. Generally, line ministries are accountable to the Government for their performance in service

provision, even if services are paid for by NERCHA or international donors (indicated as 'low accountability').

Figure 6.1 Coordination, Financial Flows and Accountability for HIV/AIDS, Swaziland, 2009

Major international donors such as the UN agencies, the US government, the EU, and International Foundations most often have independent systems for funding and management of HIV and AIDS activities that largely fall outside the national structures. The dominant financial modalities used to channel resources from these donors to the service providers are either through direct contract or through intermediary organizations such as HAPAC for the EU; and Pac and FLAS for US government funding (UNAIDS and Accenture 2007).

Funds allocated by the government and international partners for activities in HIV and AIDS has been increased significantly since 2002/03¹³, from SZL 13,9 Million to SZL 143,2 million in 2007/2008. Yet, absorption capacity remained quite low: SZL 31,6 million was carried forward from 2006/07 to 2007/08 (79% of funds used), and SZL 49,9 million was carried forward from 2007/08 to 2008/09 (74% of funds used) (NERCHA 2009).

Costs for administration such as reported by NERCHA are relatively high, certainly variable over years, going from 15% over 7% to 12% in respectively FY 2004/2005, FY2005/06 and FY2006/07. 'Other costs' stood at 21% in FY 2004/05 (NERCHA 2009).

The systemic arrangements for HIV/AIDS coordination, financing, management and delivery are likely to explain the level and trend of coordination costs, which given the complex nature of the financing flows are very likely under-reported. The Accenture report observed: "Funds filter down through a complex network of pipes with funding flows following intricate paths

¹³ NURCHE Annual report 2007/08; The kingdom of Swaziland, 2009

through various intermediary organizations and out through different bureaucracies to recipient organizations¹⁴. Multiple intermediary disbursement bodies add additional administrative costs decreasing the efficiency of AIDS finance.

Moreover, in a country, ranked 121 out of 163 on a corruption perception scale by Transparency International (MOEP&D and the European Community 2007) the current coordination and financial flow arrangements do increase the risk of use of funds for unintended purposes, further decreasing the efficiency of each dollar invested in HIV and AIDS.

HIV and AIDS spending categories and resource allocation

As discussed in previous sections, all major actors in HIV and AIDS in Swaziland plan and report activities against different spending sub-categories. At the operational level this makes the planning process exceedingly complex and it is virtually impossible to purposefully plan activities in any detailed way. The misaligned approaches to planning undermine the effectiveness of finance for HIV and AIDS in Swaziland and they're at odds with the Three Ones Principles and the Paris Declaration.

The result of a fragmented approach to planning and budgeting is seen in the resource allocation patterns for HIV and AIDS. The NASA, which converted all spending by different actors into one joint reporting framework (which it has been said strangely does not correspond with the NSP activity categories), reveals that spending generally is not in line with the NSP. For example, in FY 2006/07 there was a very significant overspent on OVC and an underspent on care and treatment. While different reasons explain this observation, the outstanding one is undoubtedly that the AIDS Response in Swaziland does not have the tools to make sure that resources are allocated following the plan (NERCHA 2008).

Recipients

The NASA distinguishes between 6 main categories of beneficiaries¹⁵ (NERCHA 2008). In FY 2006/07 41% of funds were targeted at PLWHA, 34% to vulnerable populations mainly OVC, 23% to the general population and 2% to 'specific accessible populations'.

It is important to make a careful distinction between the intention to target funds to certain population groups, and the actual reception of goods and services for a corresponding budget by these population groups. The data available report on intentional spending; there're no data available on the extent to which beneficiaries receive intended goods and services.

Yet, expenditure tracking surveys in other sectors have repeatedly found that sometimes considerable portions of funds leak out of the system in the funding channel from financing source to beneficiary. In Zambia in 2001, for example, 76% of non-wage grants and 10% of fixed school grants were spent on intended beneficiaries. For non-wage expenditure in Ghana and Tanzania, this was respectively 49% and 57%, both in 1998 (R. Reinnikka and Smith 2004). These are very significant leakages that helped explain why expected

¹⁴ UNAIDS and ACENTURE; Financial Flow Project, Swaziland; Findings and Recommendations; Draft; Feb, 2007

¹⁵ (1) people living with HIV /AIDS, (2) high risk populations (i.e. injecting drug users, sex workers, men who have sex with men and their clients) (3) vulnerable population (i.e. OVC, refugees, children born or to be born by HIV mothers and internally displaced migrants), (4) specific accessible populations (youth in school, factory employee, military and internally displaced migrants), (5) general population; and (6) other beneficiaries not classified above.

outcomes in education did not materialise. It is not suggested that leakage or capture of HIV and AIDS funds in Swaziland is important, but it is important to emphasise that at present no data are available on the share of funds that arrive at beneficiary level. The NASA should consider exploring this in following rounds.

6.3.4 Implementation

Implementing any social policy or intervention faces a range of challenges. This is not different for the implementation of HIV and AIDS interventions in Swaziland and illustrated by the National Composite Policy index 2007 scores on “efforts to enforce the existing policies, laws and regulations” which stand at 3 out of 10, zero being the lowest score, and by the scores on “efforts in the implementation of treatment, care and support programmes in 2007” which also rate 3 out of 10 and haven’t improved since 2005 (NERCHA 2008).

Underperformance in service delivery is due to a number of reasons some of which are discussed in turn below. Most illustrations borrowed below are from the health sector, which however, is important for HIV and AIDS service delivery. Moreover, we assume they broadly apply to the implementation of HIV and AIDS services at large.

Systemic arrangements to respond to HIV/AIDS

A number of sectors contribute to the state of public health in Swaziland: the MoHSW is responsible for delivering health services; the Ministry of Public Services for employing health workers; the Ministry of Works for repair and maintenance of buildings and Equipment; the Ministry of Education for pre-service training of physicians, nurses and other health workers(MOEP&D and the European Community 2007). This fragmented approach to health service delivery contributes to important levels of operational inefficiencies, staff shortages, inappropriate staff deployment, non-functioning equipment and obsolete infrastructure.

Health sector institutional constraints

The health system is highly decentralized in Swaziland. Regional Management Committees are established to manage the health centres and clinics in their zone. Nevertheless, the committees do not make resource allocation decisions, which are centrally controlled by the MoHSW. This is a cumbersome procedure discouraging local initiatives and preventing the rapid implementation of decisions (MOEP&D and the European Community 2007; Whiteside and Whalley 2007).

The MoHSW with its current capacity and organisational set-up is constrained in exercising its stewardship function. The lack of leadership and coordination in the sector contributes to the inability to address health system problems and ultimately the health needs of population. Though Government has embarked on reorganizing and restructuring the MoHSW, the health system is still largely considered as inefficient and irresponsive (Health and Development Africa (pty) and JTK Associate 2005)

Oversight and delivery of HIV/AIDS services

HIV and AIDS service delivery is fragmented and no single entity, neither national nor international, has overall responsibility. Most multilateral and bilateral donors, international NGOs and foundations are using their own systems for administration of service delivery, and subcontract with service providers. In the case of the Global Fund the scenario is more complicated as NERCHA is in charge to channel resource to mainly public HIV and AIDS service providers but these providers are consequently mostly accountable to the MoHSW, or other technical line ministries.

Moreover, since service providers tend to be predefined in Global Fund proposals, and since it is almost unprecedented that they are held accountable for under-performance, there's little or no real accountability attached to this kind of funding. As such it is informally acknowledged that Global Fund finance leaves much more degree of freedom to the service provider than other sources of funding do, including public sources. This suggests that there's room to standardise service provision administrative regimes and accountability processes that embody incentive mechanisms that improve service delivery.

Financial Management and administration of HIV/AIDS services

The MoHSW recognises important shortages in the financial planning, reporting and accounting, transparent procurement and accountability of the HIV and AIDS programme in the ministry (Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 2009). Moreover, ineffective human resources policies and delays in salary payment partly explain general low morale in health care staff; and key sub-systems for drug procurement and distribution, maintenance and transport are often not fully functional.

The MoHSW strategic plan therefore suggests to “strengthen financial management and administrative support capacity to ensure maximum accountability, efficient resource utilization and delivery of quality health services”.

6.3.5 Monitoring and Evaluation

M&E systems

NERCHA has its own Monitoring and Evaluation department which ensures the coordination of the national HIV M&E framework. The MoHSW has currently little capacity to operate an effective M&E system. Its M&E system is fragmented with responsibility split between Ministry's Health statistics Unit (HSU) and M&E Unit at SNAP. (MOEP&D and the European Community 2007). Shortages include the absence of data; poor quality of statistics; insufficient methodologies, standards and practices related to data collection, processing, analysis, and reporting; poor procedures for data flow and quality assurance; and under-utilization of data in decision making (Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 2009). The NERCHA Monitoring and Evaluation system is partly dependent on the MoHSW's HIV and AIDS M&E system to track health related indicators (NERCHA 2008).

The Swaziland HIV/AIDS Programme Monitoring System (SHAPMoS), which mostly collects non-health data, has been launched by the Ministry of Regional Development and Youth Affairs in 2006, and also engages Ministry of Education officers responsible for the monitoring of HIV and AIDS related education activities at the level of the regions.

M&E instruments

Swaziland has different M&E instruments in place. The Technical Working Group for M&E has set up the National M&E Framework for HIV/AIDS in 2005 which applies to the NSP. The first Swaziland DHS with a biological component was conducted in 2007. In 2008, with the support of UNAIDS, the first NASA was conducted to track national and international AIDS spending by categories and financial sources. Simultaneously, the National Composite Policy Index (NCPI) has been set up to examine status and progress in planning processes, political support, human rights, civil society involvement, prevention and treatment coverage, and so on.

The main data used to populate these instruments come from different sources, both routine and survey based including the Demographic and Health Survey; the Antenatal Care HIV sentinel report 2006; MoLHSW HIV/AIDS M&E routine database and HMIS; Schools life

skills and sex workers surveys; the NASA; HIV/AIDS estimates and projections (UNAIDS and NERCHA 2007) and OVC survey and client satisfaction studies.

Next steps on M&E

The different main segments of the national HIV and AIDS M&E framework has been recently assessed. These assessments have recognised that significant progress has been made at various levels of the system.

In December 2008 the MoHSW completed the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Framework 2008-2013. It aims to improve the accountability for both resources and results; and to facilitate evidence based strategic decisions making (Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 2008). The plan aims to build strong MoHLSW leadership in M&E of the entire health sector with arrangements extending to the monitoring and evaluating of the performance of health related HIV and AIDS programmes.

The new MoHSW M&E system is a welcome opportunity to reduce overlap and increase effectiveness of the overall HIV and AIDS M&E system. Especially in the early days of the system sufficient attention should be paid to ensuring optimal complementarity with the systems already in place.

The current overall M&E system also seems overly reliant on a number of what appear to be ad-hoc surveys and reports. Vital information for monitoring and evaluation of the AIDS Response should rely on routine data sources.

7 Absorptive capacity

A detailed analysis of the absorptive capacity of the HIV and AIDS service delivery system in Swaziland is beyond the scope of this work. Nevertheless, the question whether the system can effectively spend an additional dollar for HIV and AIDS is crucial when thinking about AIDS financing.

At a general level, the Public Expenditure Review (World Bank 2006) concludes that governance in Swaziland is poor and corruption is widespread. The WBI Comparative Governance Indicators 2004 show that 'government effectiveness' was the weakest in a regional comparison with Botswana, Namibia, Lesotho and South Africa; and that government effectiveness had actually deteriorated between 1998 and 2004. The PER also found that budget credibility, the extent to which actual expenditure are close to budgeted expenditures unless exceptional circumstances justify important deviations, is low.

Of more direct important to the AIDS Response the health sector capacity to deliver quality services in an efficient way has received increasing attention as indicators suggest structural and deep-rooted absorption problems.

Swaziland has committed to the Abuja declaration and strives to allocate 15% of public expenditure to the health sector. That is why the budgetary allocation to the Ministry of Health has been gradually increased between FY 2005/06 and FY 2007/08. However, the Ministry of Health has not been able to spend the additional resources, which give rise to a consequential remark in the Budget Outlook Paper FY2009/10 : "It is very important for the Ministry of Health to ensure that this translates into improvements in service delivery as it will be difficult to justify the increases if that is not the case."

However, the quality of health services leaves a lot to be desired, due to dilapidated infrastructure, drug shortages and human resource constraints. The latter are particularly acute in Swaziland. There're an estimated 1.8 per 10,000 doctors and 28 per 10,000 nurses. Of the 3,261 nurses registered by the nursing council in 2003, only 758 were employed in the public and mission facilities bringing the nurse/population ratio down to 7 per 10,000. In 2004 40% of the doctors' posts and 17% of those of nurses were vacant. There're only 15 ART doctors in the entire country.

Apart from an acute crisis in the number, quality, motivation and allocation of health workers in the country, the health systems faces numerous other challenges including drug shortages, below-standard patient care, lack of appropriate medical equipment, long queues, ill-functioning referral process and lack of follow up, unclean health facilities, inadequate water supplies, weak management, outdated systems, absence of a replacement strategy for medical equipment, amongst others (World Bank 2006; World Bank 2007; NERCHA 2008; Ministry of Health and Social Welfare 2009).

In a context characterised by generalised poor governance and by a severely constrained health system, NERCHA as an institution is doing surprisingly well. At the onset, a number of teething problems have been signalled including lack of capacity to channel Global Fund funding to civil society organisations. However, since FY 2006/07 NERCHA has been able to fully spent its resource allocation from the Government, and target gap of the AIDS Response, defined as the difference between a target set at the beginning and end of a planning period, is small in a regional comparison with 11 other countries.

However, even if NERCHA has increased its capacity in certain essential managerial areas the scaling-up of the AIDS Response will be hampered by what appears to be an exceptionally weak health system.

Swaziland is far from the only country facing this dilemma. A common, and often successful strategy, is to closely associate the private for profit and the non-profit, especially CSO active in HIV and AIDS, to the delivery of AIDS services. However, many CSO in Swaziland face capacity constraints as well. This has motivated NERCHA at some point to move into service delivery itself, and become an implementing partner for the Global Fund. The effectiveness of this strategy is however questionable for two reasons:

- NERCHA's capacity to effectively coordinate the Response is hampered by being involved in implementation. Many actors believe that NERCHA cannot cumulate the function of financing agent, where it is responsible for allocating resources to service providers, and the function of service provider. If NERCHA is to credibly exercise its coordination function it will have to withdraw from implementation.
- NERCHA's involvement in implementation is only defensible as a short term stop-gap strategy to make up for acute lack of service delivery capacity. However, the only

route to building up long term service delivery capacity in the country is to gradually build this capacity in the appropriate actors which are apart from the Ministry of Health are CSO, and the private for profit providers for some services. This urgently requires a policy shift, and a plan where resources are devoted to building up additional service delivery capacity in CSO, and the private for profit sector.

The current national plan goes some way in recognising and addressing capacity issues in the country, and it does propose to build on civil society organisations and the private sector for the delivery of services.

However, the need to build capacity in CSO is rather implicitly assumed and the question therefore remains if the national plan is bold enough to overcome Swaziland's tremendous capacity problems. If the answer to this question is no, then an additional dollar spent on HIV and AIDS in Swaziland will not easily translate into more individuals enjoying more quality HIV and AIDS services.

8 Equity

Equity considerations have not been of major concern in the AIDS Response in Swaziland up till now. Little to no research has examined whether those with HIV and AIDS related needs in Swaziland have access to HIV and AIDS services independently of their wealth or place of living. However, there is reason to believe that the AIDS Response in Swaziland is not equitable.

Household out-of-pocket health expenditure is the highest in the region, and increased from 1998 to 2002. This suggests that households have increasingly taken on a larger share of health care funding as public and donor spending gradually shrank in that period. Moreover, indirect evidence suggests that public health expenditure in Swaziland is geared more towards wealthier segments of the population (World Bank 2006). This is particularly worrying in a country with a high income inequality since public expenditure is one of the few means to enhance equity.

We have no specific evidence on health related HIV and AIDS expenditure in Swaziland but studies in other countries have shown that poorer households tend to shoulder the highest burden. In 2002 households in Kenya, Rwanda and Zambia paid between 15% and 25% of these costs out-of-pocket. In comparison with the general population PLWHA spent up to about 6 times more out-of-pocket on health services than the general population (Ministry of Health and PHRplus 2005; De 2006). This directly implies that poorer households will have much more difficulties to cope with these expenditures, in many cases not be able to generate sufficient funds and therefore access less HIV and AIDS services compared to richer households. Moreover, analysis from previous global economic crises shows that the impact on health outcomes is typically worse in poorer households following a decrease in the use of health services. Future modifications to AIDS financing in Swaziland will have to be assessed on their potential to be equity enhancing.

9 Building blocks of an HIV and AIDS financing strategy

This work has examined the current AIDS financing strategy from different angles. The underlying objective was to identify the next steps to ensuring that the financing strategy contributes to an effective, efficient and equitable AIDS Response. Although a lot of evidence shows that significant progress has been made in little time, four major challenges stand out in the immediate future:

1. The AIDS Response faces a substantial and over time growing financing gap as there's an acute lack of projected resources to achieve Universal Access as laid out in the National Strategic Framework 2009 – 2014. The anticipated decreased availability of funds due to the global financial downturn exacerbates this challenge.
2. The capacity of the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare to deliver quality health services to the entire population is weak. This begs the question how additional resources for HIV and AIDS services will be spent effectively to increase health service availability to PLWHA.
3. Despite NERCHA's managerial capacity, important progress can be made to better coordinate the AIDS Response. This will make the allocation of resources more relevant, efficient and effective.
4. There's indirect evidence that the current financing strategy is inequitable: poorer PLWHA and affected households share a comparatively larger financial burden. The risk exists that with increasing competition for scarce resources households will end having to pay even more out-of-pocket to access HIV and AIDS services.

These challenges are both important and urgent. We identified four ways in which these challenges can be addressed in the near future: increase available resources for HIV and AIDS; engage in health system strengthening; expand absorptive capacity and introduce a form of sector wide approach. These are discussed in turn.

9.1 Mobilise additional resources for HIV and AIDS

Resource projections for FY 2013/14 show that for every USD 3.5 needed to achieve Universal Access only USD 1 will be available. If nothing is done to remedy this prospect, very tough choices regarding the services that will receive financing, and those that won't, will have to be made. However, there're several options to consider before such an detrimental scenario fully materialises:

First, as indicated by the macro economic analysis of the Swaziland's fiscal sustainability position (section 5), the authorities can consider allocating a larger share of public resources to the AIDS Response, despite the deteriorating economic and fiscal climate.

Second, Ministries of Finance are however reluctant to increase resource allocations if a number of criteria are not met. ASAP, a joint UNAIDS – World Bank programme, emphasises that national strategic plans should be (ASAP 2007):

- ✓ Selective, carefully prioritised and evidence-driven;
- ✓ Feasible, with clear and costed implementation arrangements that draw on the available implementation capacity, especially in civil society and private sector;

- ✓ Be linked to functioning and sustainable systems for monitoring, evaluation and management for results.

The AIDS Response in Swaziland can make important headway in each of these areas, and as long as it doesn't it will be exposed to the risk that the Ministry of Finance refuses to increase domestic resource provision for Swaziland.

Third, the multisectoral approach in Swaziland is hardly developed. Only recently the Public Sector HIV and AIDS Coordination Committee (PSHACC) started to look seriously at workplace policies in the ministries and public agencies. However, external mainstreaming is not yet on the agenda. However, a multisectoral approach is typically a route into involving more actors in the fight against HIV, and therefore also additional resource mobilisation (ASAP 2007). Indeed, if the government's recommendation that ministries spend 2% of their budget on HIV and AIDS would be put in practice a large additional budget for AIDS, up to about 1/3 of the current available resources, would be made available. This avenue merits further exploration.

Fourth, the private sector in Swaziland, from households over communities to businesses, is believed to contribute importantly to HIV and AIDS (see section 3.4). Yet at this moment this contribution is not recorded and hardly recognised. The next NASA would have to document the private sector's contributions so that these can be taken into account when calculating the financing gap. That analysis will also show where potential further resources may be mobilised within the Swazi society, and policies with incentives to stimulate private sector contributions can be developed.

Fifth, innovative sources of funds should be examined more closely. Especially a Social Health Insurance Fund (or any large scale pool of resources for health) and remittance flows have an important potential to contribute significant additional resources for the AIDS Response (see section 3.5).

Last, an active advocacy policy should make donors aware of Swaziland's need for additional resources to adequately fight HIV and AIDS. With the IMF and the World Bank acknowledging the perverse effects of the country's income status on its capacity to mobilise aid, momentum is gathering to undo these consequences and have donors look for innovative ways to channel more aid to the country. Alan Whiteside has suggested to build advocacy around Swaziland's HIV and AIDS prevalence, increasing maternal mortality ratio and declining Human Development Index (Whiteside and Whalley 2007). The United Nations points at Swaziland's 'triple threat' combining a severe AIDS epidemic, deepening food insecurity and weakening government capacity (United Nations 2003). However, Swaziland's case will be even stronger if it demonstrates that it has done everything in its own power to maximise resource availability for HIV and AIDS. This not only includes raising public expenditure, but also addressing the problems of absorptive capacity and the negative effects of the AIDS Response's coordination failure.

9.2 Health system strengthening

Health system strengthening has been hotly debated in the HIV and AIDS policy and research community but it is now widely recognised that sustainability and up-scaling of AIDS Responses will necessitate the strengthening of health systems in most countries, especially those with high HIV prevalence (UNAIDS 2007; Gorik Ooms, Wim Van Damme et al. 2008; Stop AIDS Campaign 2008). This had been recognised by world's two of biggest vertical programmes and GFATM began funding health system strengthening in 2005 and

PEPFAR II also includes support for complementarity and linkages with core health programmes including resources to ease the health worker crisis.

The Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Swaziland, a key player in scaling up the AIDS Response battles with myriad inter-linked problems that are unlikely to go away soon. The new National Health Sector Strategic Plan provides a good start to dealing with these, but the risk is that without additional focus and effort the current approach by the Ministry of Health will be too little too late for the AIDS Response.

Swaziland recognises this in the National Strategic Framework and the Round 8 Global Fund proposal and part of the current PEPFAR grant contain health system strengthening components. However, these remain quite modest. The central question is therefore whether enough is currently being done to increase the capacity of the HIV and AIDS service delivery system in Swaziland so that an extra dollar for HIV and AIDS is effectively and efficiently spent. Given the tremendous problems of its health system, the answer is likely no. Therefore it should be seriously considered to allocate more resources mobilised within the AIDS Response to health system strengthening.

9.3 Increase Civil Society Organisations' involvement

The analysis above has shown that CSO are too weakly involved in the HIV and AIDS policy planning processes and in the delivery of the AIDS Response. This seems to sprout from a deep-rooted way of working in public policy in Swaziland. However, increasing the meaningful involvement of CSO in the policy and delivery of the Response seems to be a powerful strategy at this stage in the AIDS Response for two reasons:

- The only way to ensure long term sustainability of the national HIV and AIDS policy is to associate all national stakeholders in the process. While this is currently being done on paper, and real progress has been made, a level of mutual distrust between the leading public agencies and the CSO seem to persist and prevent full and meaningful participation of the CSO in the policy process.
- The Ministry of Health and Social Welfare faces critical capacity constraints for the delivery of HIV and AIDS services, and hence the scaling up of the Response. Because of the equally weak implementing capacity in CSO, NERCHA has stepped in as an implementing partner, but this cannot be a sustainable long term approach, as it prevents NERCHA from ensuring effectively its coordination function. While the Ministry of Health in its recent policy is serious about capacity strengthening, it is imperative in order to create sufficient capacity in the country for CSO to be strengthened, so that they, alongside the private for profit sector and the Ministry of Health, can ensure the delivery of sufficient quality HIV and AIDS services to PLWHA and affected households.

For these reasons the increased involvement of CSO in the policy process and the delivery of HIV and AIDS services is critical for the sustainability and the scaling up of the AIDS Response in Swaziland.

9.4 Programme Based Approach

As shown by the evolution of important UNGASS indicators, Swaziland has made some significant progress in moving towards Universal Access. NERCHA is seen to master essential managerial processes, perhaps the most impressive illustration of which is the

achievements made in the Policy Development and Monitoring and Evaluation areas. However, the analysis above shows that while improvements have been made at the top-end of the policy process (policies of major players are reasonably well aligned with the NSF) and its tail-end (M&E), the institutional arrangements of the AIDS Response in the coordination, resource allocation and implementation phases of the policy cycle are such that the AIDS response is only weakly effective and efficient. More precisely:

- NERCHA's coordination role is undermined by the overlapping of mandates with other coordinating bodies including the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare leading to coordination failure;
- Almost all actors in the HIV and AIDS Response in Swaziland use their own funding and implementation mechanisms and procedures. Funding flows follow complicated paths through various intermediary organizations and bureaucracies to recipient organizations. This not only adds to the administrative cost of implementing the Response, and the consequential wasteful loss of scarce resources, more importantly it prevents anybody to know whether resources are actually allocated following the priorities of the National Strategic Plan;

Fragmented programme delivery is, unfortunately, quite common in many countries and its detrimental consequences on effectiveness and efficiency have attracted quite some interest in light of measuring progress on the Paris Declaration. Generally it is observed that fragmented programme implementation leads to:

- Diminished country ownership, undermined national planning and budgeting processes, reduced focus and coherence of efforts in the sector;
- Multiple donor implementation coordination units translate into high transaction costs, and impose additional management costs on government counterparts;
- The quality of the policy dialogue tends to suffer;
- Missed opportunity to strengthen public planning and implementation mechanisms perpetuating national capacity constraints;

Swaziland also suffers these negative consequences of a fragmented approach and at the most fundamental level they stand in the way of translating money into results. The answer in other countries, including some in the region, has been to move to some sort of programme based approach (PBA). Programme based approaches can take many forms going from general and sector budget support to SWAPs. SWAPs are coordinating mechanisms where support to a particular sector is improved through better policy dialogue and coordination of aid directed to national sector plans and is often a prelude to, or comprises of some form of, pooled funding and the use of public systems to disburse these funds to service providers. The advantages associated with PBA include:

- By directing resources through national systems, institutional reform and capacity development is supported and sometimes accelerated;
- Provides a more effective platform for policy dialogue and raises domestic accountability and ownership;
- Leads to mutual accountability between donors and national agencies, and increased predictability of funds

- Supports a coherent approach to the programming of resources;
- Transaction costs will be lower as national systems are used instead of a multitude of duplicate systems being established.

It is clear that the anticipated effects of a PBA would address important weaknesses in the AIDS Response identified earlier on in this document. Programme based approaches, however, have also met with criticism and their potential downsides must be recognised when designing them. Ooms has clearly pointed out a potentially important issue with the evolution from off budget to on budget aid. In many countries fiscal sustainability considerations leave apart Global Fund contributions. However, when moving to a form of pooled funding the risk increases that these are taken into account, leading to some form of fiscal constraint and virtual spending cap (Gorik Ooms 2008). The direct, and perverse, effect of moving currently off-budget funds onto the budget would be that fewer resources are being made available for the AIDS Response because macro economic prudence would suggest limiting spending to preserve macro economic stability.

Whether or not this scenario applies to Swaziland is difficult to predict as it depends on the extent to which external resources are currently on budget, and the position regarding fiscal sustainability taken by the national authorities and influential international bodies such as the IMF. The first factor merits analysis beyond the scope of this work; the second factor is not set in stone as different options and recommendations have been applied to seemingly similar cases (The World Bank 2006). The recommendation of this work is therefore to stick with the adagio that the *proof of the pudding is in the eating*: any PBA approach must be well prepared, and part of that preparation is to assess the likely consequences on the fiscal sustainability position of the country. Views from national and international stakeholders on the latter are partly subjective and other countries that have gone through implementing programme based approaches in AIDS have found satisfactory solutions.

Another potential downside of PBA is that the role of national agencies, in this case NERCHA, in orienting policy and resource allocation is likely to increase. While this is an intended benefit of PBA, it is important that civil society organisations are sufficiently associated in the policy process because they often defend the rights of marginalised groups such as MSM, commercial sex workers and IDUs that would otherwise be under-represented in the Response (Stop AIDS Campaign 2008; The International HIV/AIDS Alliance 2008). The implementation of a PBA in Swaziland should therefore go hand in hand with the increased involvement of CSO in the planning and implementation processes of the AIDS Response.

A last criticism of PBA lies in the reason why vertical programmes, including the Global Fund and PEPFAR, two of Swaziland's most important donors in HIV and AIDS, have been put in place. Vertical programmes have been called to live because national systems including their donors were unable to tackle what is seen as major public health crises. Vertical programmes bypass national planning and implementation systems if they are seen as ineffective to actually achieve tangible results within acceptable timeframes. While the vertical approaches to HIV and AIDS in Swaziland have delivered results on the ground, they are now however probably hitting constraints imposed by an insufficient health system and are preventing to reach the next level of efficiency that comes from unified planning and implementation systems.

The Global Fund has recognised the shortcomings of its approach in some contexts and in order to support national planning processes, for example, it allows the introduction of costed action plans as funding proposals under certain conditions. Swaziland should consider this

option. And in countries such as Mozambique and Malawi the Global Fund has participated in forms of programme based approaches. These experiences are broadly seen as positive and could provide inspiration to Swaziland (Clare Dickinson, Javier Martinez et al. 2007; Gorik Ooms 2008; Gorik Ooms, Wim Van Damme et al. 2008).

Putting in place a PBA is often seen as a major enterprise and requires sufficient preparation. However, browsing through what many authors see as pre-conditions, it appears that many of them are met in Swaziland, such as an improving monitoring and evaluation system, a suitable annual national plan and a donor group that meets regularly. Others, however, aren't but don't seem insurmountable as they can be worked on, such as the existence of a working common funding arrangement, a clear code of conduct and of harmonisation mechanisms and robust and transparent reporting and accounting systems (Clare Dickinson, Javier Martinez et al. 2007; Javier Martinez 2008; Katarina Kotoglou 2008; World Bank 2008). The most important missing element in setting up a PBA is political buy in, both from national actors as from donors. Experiences in other countries have shown that early donor buy-in, individuals with leadership, vision and determination to pursue PBA and agreeing on a timetable are factors contributing to their success.

Since some form of PBA will address simultaneously different severe problems the AIDS Response presently encounters, it is a particularly powerful instrument in making progress in the effective and efficient implementation of the AIDS Response in Swaziland.

10 References

- Andrew Mold, Sebastian Paulo, et al. (2009). "Taking stock of the credit crunch: implications for development finance and global governance." OECD Development Centre Working paper 277.
- ASAP (2007). Preparing National HIV/AIDS Strategies and Action Plans - Lessons of Experience.
- Central Statistical Office and Macro International Inc. (2008). Swaziland Demographic and Health Survey 2006-2007.
- Clare Dickinson, Javier Martinez, et al. (2007). The Global Fund operating in a SWAp through a common fund: issues and lessons from Mozambique, HLSP Institute.
- De, S. (2006). "National Resource Flows for HIV/AIDS in Kenya, Rwanda, and Zambia: A Comparative Analysis."
- DeLeon Peter and Kaufmanis Katie (2001). "Public Policy Theory: Will It Play in Peoria?" Policy Currents 10(4).
- Enrico Pavignani (2009). Understanding Health Policy Processes, WHO.
- Finmark Trust (2003). "Finscope 2003: Profiling Demand for Financial Services in Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, and Swaziland."
- Genesis Analytics (2006). "Facilitating Southern African remittance networks – An issues paper for the 2006 SADC Commonwealth Secretariat workshop on remittances."
- Global development finance (2008). Financial flows to developing countries: recent trends and prospects, The World Bank Group.
- Gorik Ooms (2008). The right to health and the sustainability of healthcare: Why a new global health aid paradigm is needed., University of Ghent.
- Gorik Ooms, Wim Van Damme, et al. (2008). "The 'diagonal' approach to Global Fund financing: a cure for the broader malaise of health systems?" Globalization and Health 4(6).
- Health and Development Africa (pty) and JTK Associate (2005). Study of the health service burden of HIV/AIDS and impact of HIV/AIDS on Health sector in Swaziland.
- IMF (2004). Article IV Consultation.
- IMF (2006). Impact of remittances on Poverty and Financial Development in Sub Saharan Africa. IMF Working Paper 07/38.
- IMPA (2003). "Indicators for Policy management: MDGs and Statistical literacy."
- Javier Martinez (2008). How external support for health and HIV will evolve as Viet Nam becomes a middle-income country, HLSP Institute.

Katarina Kotoglou (2008). Independent monitoring on the implementation of the Hanoi core statements at sectoral and sub-national level in Vietnam, Oxford Policy Management.

Lasswell, H. (1956). The decision process: seven categories of functional analysis, College park, Md., University of Maryland.

Ministry of Economic Planning and Development and Poverty reduction task force (2005). "Action Programme For Reduction of Poverty 2005-2015".

Ministry of Finance (2008). Budget Outlook Paper 2009/2010 - 2011/2012.

Ministry of Health and Abt Associates (2007). Malawi National Health Accounts (NHA) 2002-2004 with sub-accounts for HIV and AIDS, reproductive and child health.

Ministry of Health and PHRplus (2005). Kenya National Health Accounts 2002: Estimating Expenditures on General Health and HIV/AIDS Care.

Ministry of Health and Social Welfare (2008). The Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Framework 2008-2013.

Ministry of Health and Social Welfare (2009). "National Health Sector Strategic Plan 2008-2013; Final Draft."

MOEP&D and the European Community (2007). Country Strategy paper and national indicative programme for 2008-2013. The Kingdom of Swaziland and the European Community.

MoEP&D and UN resident coordinator (2005). United Nations Development assistance Framework; the Kingdom of Swaziland 2006-2010.

NERCHA (2005). Costed Action Plan for The National Multi-Sectoral Strategic Framework for HIV and AIDS, 2006-2008.

NERCHA (2008). Monitoring the declaration of commitment on HIV/AIDS (UNGASS). Swaziland Country Report.

NERCHA (2008). National AIDS Spending Assessment 2005/07 and 2006/07.

NERCHA (2009). Current Global Fund Funding excluding Round 8, TB and Malaria.

NERCHA (2009). The National Multi-sectoral Strategic Framework for HIV and AIDS 2009 - 2014.

NERCHA (2009). "NERCHA Annual Report 2007/08."

ONUSIDA (1999). "La riposte des ménages et des communautés à l'épidémie de VIH/SIDA dans les zones rurales de l'Afrique subsaharienne."

Paul A Sabatier (2007). Theories of the Policy Process.

PEPFAR (2008). Fiscal year 2008: PEPFAR Operational plan.

Peter Piot (2008). AIDS: Exceptionalism revisited, London School of Economics. **Lecture transcript.**

R. Reinnikka and N. Smith (2004). Public Expenditure tracking surveys in education, International Institute for Educational Planning.

Stop AIDS Campaign (2008). "HIV & Health Systems Strengthening. Opportunities for achieving universal access by 2010."

The International HIV/AIDS Alliance (2007). Scoping trip report (personal communication).

The International HIV/AIDS Alliance (2008). "The importance of Budget Support in securing long term commitment to national HIV and AIDS responses."

The World Bank (2006). Health financing revisited. A practitioner's guide, The World Bank.

Tim Hughes et al (2006). "Gender, Remittances and Development – Preliminary Findings from selected SADC Countries."

UNAIDS (2001). Paying for HIV/AIDS Services. Lessons from National Health Accounts and community-based health insurance in Rwanda, 1998-1999.

UNAIDS (2006). "Helping Ourselves:Community Responses to AIDS in Swaziland."

UNAIDS (2007). "Financial resources required to achieve universal access to HIV prevention, treatment, care and support."

UNAIDS and Accenture (2007). UNAIDS Accenture Financial Flow Project: Swaziland - Findings and Recommendations. UNAIDS Regional Support Team Eastern and Southern Africa. The occasional papers series.

UNAIDS and NERCHA (2007). Swaziland HIV Estimates and Projections Report.

United Nations (2003). "High Level Committee on Programmes - Swaziland."

United Nations (2006). UNDAF: United Nations Development Assistance framework, The Kingdom of Swaziland 2006-2010.

United Nations (2008). JMT and JUTA Retreat on strategic formulation of the Joint UN programme of support on HIV and AIDS (JUNPS).

Walt G and Gilson L (1994). "Reforming the health sector in developing countries: the central role of policy analysis." Health Policy and Planning 9(4): 353-70.

Whiteside, A. and A. Whalley (2007). "Reviewing 'Emergencies' for Swaziland. Shifting the Paradigm in a New Era."

WHO (2008). Feasibility assessment and financial projection results for a Social Health Insurance Scheme in Swaziland.

World Bank (2006). "Public Expenditure Review. Strengthening Public Expenditure Policy and Management for Service Delivery and Poverty Reduction."

World Bank (2006). Swaziland - Public Expenditure Review. Strengthening Public Expenditure Policy and Management for Service Delivery and Poverty Reduction.

World Bank (2007). Our Commitment: The World Bank's Africa Region HIV/AIDS Agenda for Action 2007-2011.

World Bank (2008). "Swaziland. World Bank HIV and AIDS identification Mission. Aide Memoire."

World Bank (2008). World Development Indicators.

A.1 Assumptions underpinning resource projection

The projections of resource need and availability are based on a number of hypotheses:

If figures were available for calendar years they assumed identical for fiscal years. In Swaziland calendar and fiscal years overlap for 9/12.

The exchange rates applied are those used in NASA and in the costed Action Plan, and are taken from CurrencyGP/GRAB.

The contributions from the Ministry of Finance are obtained by applying the growth rate of total expenditure such as presented in the Budget Outlook Papers to the contribution of the Ministry of Finance in the NASA.

The contribution from the UN under UNDAF is obtained by taking the UNDAF commitment for 2006-2010, deducting funds already spent, and dividing the remainder budget equally over the remaining UNDAF period. For the years 2011 and onwards, a 20% reduction in contribution is assumed, following personal communications from UN representatives that the current budget was likely to be cut as a consequence of the global financial crisis.

Global Fund contributions are communicated by the Global Fund (see section 3.3 for details).

EU contributions are obtained by distributing the committed funds equally over the period 2008-2013. For subsequent years no budget cuts are assumed.

PEPFAR contributions follow communications by PEPFAR officials (see section 3.3 for details).

For contributions from all other sources an (absolute) identical increase has been assumed between FY 05/06 and FY 06/07; and between FY 06/07 and FY 07/08. Thereafter no increase has been assumed.

A.2 Resource projections FY 2005/06 to FY 2013/14

USD	2005/06	2006/07	2007/08	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14
RN - NAC					151,946,636	214,089,424	282,898,017	311,187,819	342,306,600
Ministry of Finance	10,924,000	19,559,424	20,245,577	21,488,208	23,935,910	28,724,434	37,439,334	37,439,334	37,439,334
UN	3,520,620	4,262,229		6,500,000	11,285,962	11,285,962	6,705,000	6,705,000	6,705,000
GF	18,801,265	15,509,722		13,900,000	33,948,792	28,705,064	17,796,878	14,891,446	16,804,147
EU	0	472,137		3,864,000	4,830,000	4,830,000	4,830,000	4,830,000	4,830,000
US	1,010,997	1,928,623		12,700,000	27,800,000	27,800,000	27,800,000	27,800,000	27,800,000
Other	4,133,938	7,714,792	11,986,522	11,295,645	11,295,645	11,295,645	11,295,645	11,295,645	11,295,645
Resource availability	38,390,821	49,446,927			113,096,309	112,641,105	105,866,856	102,961,424	104,874,125
Financing gap					-38,850,327	-101,448,319	-177,031,160	-208,226,394	-237,432,475
1 USD = SAR	6.7	7	8	9.5	9.5	8.5	7	7	7
1 Euro = SAR			11.4	11.4	11.4	11.4	11.4	11.4	11.4
1 Euro = USD			1.38	1.38	1.38				